

European
Network of
Living Labs

MEMBERS CATALOGUE

2024

European Network of Living Labs

Living Lab Community

The international, non-profit, independent association of benchmarked Living Labs.

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This report is a compilation of activities of the Network for the year 2023.

Editors:

Alessandra Tricarico

Andrada Barata

Gabriella Quaranta

Michelle González Torres

Leidy Vanessa Enriquez Florez

Contributors:

Martina Desole

Evdokimos Konstantinidis

Design: Andrada Barata

Evdokimos Konstantinidis
Chairperson of ENoLL

Networking is a process of building relationships, and the strongest relationships are those nurtured over time. This is precisely what ENoLL has been dedicated to over the past 15 years. We have fostered an open, trustful, innovative, and transparent environment for our over 500 historically labelled members. In our Network, each member contributes value to the whole, while the Network, in turn, creates value for each of its members.

Our ever-expanding Network operates as a distributed innovation ecosystem. Each of our members is deeply connected to their local community stakeholders, as well as to other Living Labs within the Network. This dynamic facilitates the bottom-up flow of knowledge and information, while also enabling the top-down dissemination of policies and best practices. Our certification process ensures that all members meet the rigorous criteria of Living Labs, maintaining the highest quality of services and procedures.

ENoLL's strategic objective is to create new value, visibility, and opportunities for our Network, solidifying our position as the leading global actor for Living Labs by fostering international collaborations. Notably, more than 20% of our Network now comprises Living Labs from across the globe, extending well beyond Europe. A growing Network is a healthy Network, rich in value for its members. And that is exactly what our Network embodies.

Empower everyone to innovate!

Martina Desole
Directore of ENoLL

It is with great pleasure that I welcome you to explore the latest edition of the ENoLL Members' Catalogue.

This updated Catalogue highlights the remarkable work of over one hundred Living Labs from across the globe, all dedicated to empowering people to innovate. Each Living Lab featured here is an integral part of our Network, showcasing their unique areas of expertise and primary fields of work.

The strength of our Network lies in the diversity and interdisciplinary nature of our Living Labs, coupled with their unwavering commitment to open innovation, knowledge exchange, collaborative efforts, and social responsibility.

As you browse through this Catalogue, I encourage you to identify potential partners for your future endeavors. Whether you are an existing Living Lab or an organization interested in joining our Network, you are invited to become part of an international community that collaborates on research, projects, sustainability initiatives, and more. The Network is here to facilitate connections, foster cooperation, and advocate for the Living Lab approach on a global scale.

We take immense pride in our Members and in ENoLL's continued growth, as the true power of the Network is the Network itself!

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What we do

The European Network of Living Labs (ENoLL) is the **international, non-profit, independent association of certified Living Labs**.

Our objective is to foster the **global development of Living Labs** as open innovation ecosystems based on co-creation and cross border & cross-sectoral collaboration.

Our mission is to **provide value to our members and external stakeholders** by offering them opportunities to develop their capacities & knowledge.

More specifically, we support our members in the **development of impactful, innovative products & services**, allowing them to expand their own value to their own stakeholders and facilitating knowledge exchange among members and externals.

As a consequence, we regularly engage with our members through member **catch-up sessions**, which provide a time for the exchange of information.

ENoLL counts today more than **160 (one hundred and sixty) active members from 38 (thirty-eight) countries** located on **five continents** (more than five hundred historically labelled members worldwide). Our aim is to influence the development of cross-regional instruments to enable and speed up cooperation, piloting and methodology creation of the Living Lab concept globally.

ENoLL is integrated into four main groups:

- ENoLL Board of the Association
- ENoLL General Assembly
- ENoLL Office
- ENoLL Members

WHAT IS ENOLL

ENoLL Board of Association

The Association is managed by the Board of the Association comprising at least three and a maximum of twenty-one Directors, appointed by the General Assembly. The Board of the Association meets at least once every three months, including meetings by telephone, electronic means or any other means. The Board of the Association elects among the Directors, a Chairperson of the Board of the Association, a Secretary and a Treasurer. The positions of Chairperson, Secretary and Treasurer are subject to a yearly election.

ENoLL General Assembly

The General Assembly is composed of all Effective Members and meets every year, under the chairpersonship of the Chairperson of the Board of the Association or in their absence the eldest of the Directors at the registered office or at the place indicated in the notice of the meeting. The decisions of the General Assembly are binding to all Effective Members, Adherent Members and Innovation Partners. The General Assembly has amongst others such powers as approval of the annual budgets and annual accounts, election, dismissal and discharge of Directors, modification of the Statutes, admission of an Effective Member, Adherent Member or Innovation Partner, upon proposal from the Board of the Association etc.

ENoLL Office

The role of the ENoLL Office is to implement decisions passed by the General Assembly and run day-to day operations of the Network.

ENoLL Office is located at Avenue des Arts 6, 1210 Saint-Josse-ten-Noode, Brussels, Belgium.

WHAT IS A LIVING LAB

Living Labs

Living Labs are open innovation ecosystems in real-life test and experimentation environments based on a systematic user co-creation approach that integrates research and innovation activities in communities, placing citizens at the center of innovation, fostering co-creation and open innovation among the main actors of the Quadruple Helix Model, namely:

- Citizens,
- Government,
- Industry,
- Academia.

Living Labs focus on co-creation, rapid prototyping & testing and scaling up innovations & businesses, providing different types of joint value to the involved stakeholders.

A Living Lab can be initiated and hosted by a university, city, research institute, municipality, or any organisation where the user is placed at the center of the innovation process.

In this context, Living Labs operate as intermediaries/orchestrators among citizens, government, industry and academia.

In this catalogue, ENOLL showcases its members worldwide, working in different countries and representing a broad range of thematic domains.

ENOLL WORKING GROUPS (WGS)

Working Groups

The ENOLL Working Groups focus on key topics of interest within the ENOLL Community. Both are open to members and externals who are interested in working with other experts in a specific domain. Below, the focuses of all WGs are briefly described.

- **Agriculture, Agri-food & Rural:** this working group strives to improve networking, boost connections in the sector and enhance the activities the labs are involved in by disseminating them among the members. The group welcomes all Living Labs in agriculture and similar sectors as well as organizations which aim to become a Living Lab in the future, to join our Network and meet the members of our ecosystem.
- **Culture & Co-creativity:** this working group aims to position Culture and Creativity Living Labs as drivers for the co-creation of products and services with other sectors.
- **Digital Urban Systems & Solutions for Transitions Urban Innovation:** the Digital Urban Systems & Solutions for Transitions Working Group (WG) aims to address the challenges faced by cities in establishing and maintaining effective, inclusive and dynamic urban ecosystems. Its primary objective is to strengthen ENOLL's presence in the urban innovation landscape as a supportive partner for urban ecosystems.
- **Energy & Environment:** the aim of this working group is to generate a global movement toward a more sustainable society to solve complex challenges related to energy & environment.
- **Gender in Innovation:** the goal is to build a network of stakeholders that cooperates to increase gendered innovation, advancing on research and practice, capacity building, addressing its potential for opening new markets and for solving global challenges and European priorities.
- **Harmonization:** the WG has been established to define a Harmonization Framework with suggested processes, guidelines and recommendations on how Living Labs can perform their activities in a harmonized way that is widely accepted by the Living Lab community across the world.
- **Health & Well Being:** the mission of this working group is to activate and boost a collaborative ecosystem among Living Labs interested in the domains of Health and Well Being, giving visibility of their added value at the European and international level and attracting key actors within the public and private sector.

- **Joint Working Group with the European Commission on Digital Sustainability for Zero Pollution:** the overall objective of the JWG is to define a set of recommendations together with a list of KPIs to assess their efficiency/effectiveness to help local and regional authorities to achieve a climate and environment-friendly use of digital solutions to accelerate zero pollution efforts. By raising the cities' awareness of the opportunity of using Living Labs to become green and digital, with a particular focus on citizen engagement, the Zero Pollution objectives will be more easily achieved.
- **Joint Working Group with the European Commission on Living Labs as Regulatory Learning tools:** this working group aims to explore how addressing the regulatory implications of Living Lab projects can be framed as an opportunity to enhance trust and knowledge between innovators and regulators. The goal is to collect evidence for better regulation of innovation.
- **Mobility:** in this working group we transfer knowledge and create added value for mobility Living Labs about policy frameworks, harmonization, scalability & sustainability. A common understanding of Mobility Living Labs is the basis for organizing focused discussions & Cross-Living Lab activities and for developing a joint position at EU level.
- **Social Impact of AI:** this working group aims at providing a practical approach to the questions related to the social transformations associated with the development of Artificial Intelligence, in the general framework of digital transformation.
- **Social Innovation & Digital Rights:** this working group is exploring how social innovation through Living Labs can help address societal challenges through concrete actions and by providing access for wider societies and communities to social innovation ecosystems.
- **Transition Super Living Labs:** it has been established to demonstrate the role of the Living Labs as transition accelerators that bridge bottom up and top-down policies and enable collaborative and cross sectorial innovation and synergies.

Click [HERE](#) or scan the following QR code to sign up!

Types of membership

There are four different memberships with ENOLL: **Accepted to Grow Member, Adherent Member, Effective Member, and Innovation Partner.**

Applications to become a member can be submitted **at any time**. This process, dating back to 2006, has today resulted in more than 500 historically recognised ENOLL Living Labs worldwide.

By being a Member, you become part of an **international community of Living Labs** that cooperate on research tracks, projects, acquisition and more. You can meet and talk to organisations from all over Europe and beyond. The Network is there to **ease the process of knowing each other** and collaboration through communications, events, Working Groups, etc.

Membership applications can be submitted by any legal entity from **any country in the world** that is or hosts (on behalf of a partnership) a Living Lab. This organisation will have to prove its capacity to operate as a Living Lab and/or act as an innovation service provider through the Living Lab methodology and/or develop its operations towards Living Labs.

All proposals are assessed by a panel of experts selected from within the ENOLL community in a **peer-led review process**.

Applications for Innovation Partnership can be submitted by any legal entity that is not a Living Lab and will be **evaluated by ENOLL Secretariat**.

Effective Members

The Effective members are the Adherent Members that apply for Effective Membership. Each Effective Member appoints a representative, which shall represent such Effective Member in the meetings of the General Assembly.

The Effective Members have the following rights:

- the right to attend, speak and vote at the meetings of the General Assembly,
- the right to propose a candidate for appointment as a Director,
- the right to participate into Working Groups, projects.

ENOLL MEMBERS

Adherent Members

The Adherent members are legal entities that represent a Living Lab which was duly selected according to the ENoLL labelling process for Adherent Members. During this process, applicants provide ENoLL with a membership application. If the organization fulfils the required acceptance criteria set by the ENoLL Association, Adherent Membership is granted for a period of three years.

The Adherent Members have the following rights:

- the right to attend the meetings of the General Assembly with the right to speak. For the avoidance of doubt, Adherent Members will have no right to vote at the General Assembly,
- the right to propose a candidate for appointment as a Director,
- the right to participate into Working Groups, projects.

Accepted to Grow Members

Accepted to Grow Members are organizations that represent a Living Lab, which were duly selected according to the ENoLL certification process. During this process, applicants provide ENoLL with a membership application. If the organization is not mature enough to be acknowledged as an Adherent Member but has a solid base to start from, it will become an Accepted to Grow Member. This means they will be mandatorily linked to the Capacity Building Program of ENoLL, and they'll be re-evaluated after one year.

These members are included in the ENoLL communication channels and have the right to be present and participate in the ENoLL activities, such as:

- the right to attend the meetings of the General Assembly,
- the right to participate in Working Groups.

Innovation Partners

The Innovation Partners are legal entities which are involved in the objectives and activities of the Association, which are not selected according to the ENoLL labelling process, and that apply for Innovation Partner Membership and are admitted.

Thus, Innovation Partners are not Living Labs themselves but are dedicated to supporting and developing the Living Lab community. They are companies, universities, cities & departments, among others.

The Innovation Partners have the following rights:

- the right to attend the meetings of the General Assembly with the right to speak. For the avoidance of doubt, Innovation Partners will have no right to vote at the General Assembly,
- the right to propose a candidate for appointment as a Director,
- the right to participate into Working Groups, projects.

ENoLL's Members Map

163 Active Members

From 38 countries

From 5 continents

23 Effective Members

From 14 European countries

4 Innovation Partners

From Europe

129 Adherent Members

From 35 countries

7 Accepted to Grow

From 4 countries

Areas of work

Living Labs can work in multiple areas. Most of the ENOLL members have a transversal approach that allows them to focus on more than two areas. This graph shows the different areas of work in which ENOLL members work and offer their services.

Field of expertise

Types of Living Labs

The mapping of the ENOLL members has shown a distribution of 5 main types of Living Labs.

The type of the Living Lab refers to the nature and service of each organization. Moreover, a Living Lab can belong to more than one type depending on their work. At ENOLL most of the Living Labs have pointed out their emphasis as Research Driven Living Lab and Living Lab as a service.

ANDORRA LIVING LAB

Adherent Member

Andorra Living Lab

Andorra Recerca i Innovació

Country: Andorra

www.andorralivinglab.ad

Type of Living Lab:

Country Living Lab

Andorra Living Lab is the first living lab at country scale, a space for innovation projects coordination, research, design and validation that involves all actors in the same ecosystem, enabling for development of new products and services, as well as encouraging the adoption of new technologies and in-depth reflections on them.

The country provides the opportunity to create synergies among the entrepreneurial ecosystem, promoting talent and building networks that span both social and technological aspects.

Areas of Work

- Agriculture & (Agri-)Food
- AI and Emerging technologies
- Circular Economy
- Education and/or vocational training
- Energy
- Environment/climate change
- Health & Well Being
- Regulatory learning
- SME & Start-ups
- Social innovation & inclusion
- Zero pollution & decarbonization

Main Expertise

 Living Lab Evaluation						
 User & Living Lab Research						

ANDORRA

Global Centre for Modern Ageing

Adherent Member

Global Centre for Modern Ageing

Global Centre for Modern Ageing

Country: Australia

www.gcma.net.au

Type of Living Lab:

Living testbed
Living Lab as a service
Research driven Living Lab

The Global Centre for Modern Ageing (GCMA) is a not-for-profit organisation, and its purpose is to improve the lives of older people. Through advocacy, market development, partnerships, research, and learning, GCMA helps organisations and individuals to devise, build, and commercialise products and services that allow older people to live and age well. The Living Lab has deep expertise in end-user experience research, which brings fresh, evidence-based insights to the Ageing Well industry.

Areas of Work

- AI and Emerging technologies
- Health & Well Being
- Research
- Smart Cities & Regions
- Social Innovation & Inclusion
- Other areas of work

Main Expertise

 Living Lab Evaluation						
 User & Living Lab Research						

AUSTRALIA

Adherent Member

Intergener8 Living Lab

Young and Resilient Research Centre

Country: Australia

www.westernsydney.edu.au/young-and-resilient

Type of Living Lab:

Research driven Living

The Intergener8 Living Lab is the engine room of the Young and Resilient Research Centre’s co-research and design program and was co-created in 2017 with over 100 partners. Intergener8 provides research and co-design infrastructure to bring different generations, community, industry and government stakeholders together on a flexible and ongoing basis, supported by the Co-Research and Engagement Toolkit. Intergener8 Living Lab conducts research and design programs, services and policies. It also co-creates and trials new and potentially commercialisable products that significantly boost engagement, wellbeing, resilience and entrepreneurship by harnessing the potential of technology. The Intergener8 Living Lab is a founding member of the Australian Living Labs Innovation Network and was accredited in 2019 by ENoLL. Intergener8 has delivered ten Living Lab Projects between 2019-2021.

Areas of Work

- Culture & Creativity (creative sectors)
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Environment/Climate Change
- Health & Well Being
- Media
- Social Innovation & Inclusion

Main Expertise

Adherent Member

Swinburne Living Lab

Swinburne University of Technology

Country: Australia

www.swinburne.edu.au/research/centres-groups-clinics/centre-for-design-innovation/our-research/future-self-living-lab/

Type of Living Lab:

Research driven Living Lab
Living Lab as a service

Vision of the Living Lab is Wellbeing and Enjoyment for Whole of Life. Its mission is: “Enriching everyday living of older adults through co-design”. Its objectives are: i) to enhance wellbeing of older adults through development of products, services, and experiences; ii) to become national leaders in the co-design of products, services, and experiences for the wellbeing of older adults; iii) to conduct evidence-based research on the effectiveness of products, services, and experiences for older adults; iv) to advocate on policy and funding matters for the wellbeing of older adults with funders, regulators, and peak bodies; v) to increase the recognition of the potential and impact of the Living Lab concept and practice nationally and internationally; vi) to provide training in design through workshops and other activities.

Areas of Work

- AI and Emerging technologies
- Culture & Creativity (creative sectors)
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Health & Well Being
- Mobility
- Smart Cities & Regions
- Social Innovation & Inclusion

Main Expertise

prolida

Adherent Member

Prolida - Professional Living, Innovation and Development Lab for an Ageing Society

Carinthia University of Applied Sciences

Country: Austria

www.prolida.at

Type of Living Lab:

Research driven Living Lab
Living testbed
Rural Living Lab

PROLIDA supports quadruple-helix stakeholders in the field of Health and Wellbeing (AAL/AHA) in the participative development, multi-perspective (real-life) evaluation, and long-term anchoring of innovations in the market. It focuses on technological innovations related to an active and healthy lifestyle, formal and informal care services and holistic health and wellbeing approaches.

Areas of Work

- AI and Emerging technologies
- Health & Well Being
- Rural
- Smart Cities & Regions
- Social Innovation & Inclusion

Main Expertise

 Policy Making						
 User & Living Lab Research						

AUSTRIA

Adherent Member

StadtLABOR

**StadtLABOR
Innovationen für urbane
Lebensqualität GmbH**

Country: Austria

www.stadtlaborgraz.at

Type of Living Lab:

Urban Living Lab

StadtLABOR (CityLAB) is a private innovation company working in the field of sustainable urban development. It is looking for ways in which climate protection, resource conservation and innovation can be given greater consideration in construction projects and in the development of locations, neighbourhoods, and urban districts. The vision of StadtLABOR is the liveable and sustainable city - that is resource-efficient, energy-efficient, compact, green, mixed, inclusive, and resilient. Urban quality of life requires a holistic view of the many facets of “city” - from buildings and (energy) technologies to public space, mobility and social issues. The Sustainable Development Goals adopted by the United Nations in 2016 are both an inspiration and a mission. The Living Lab follows these principles: i) long-

term partnerships: the transformation of a place takes time. It requires relationships that are supported by perseverance, a shared vision of the future and mutual trust; ii) out of the meeting room and into the place where the action is: this creates low-threshold accessible spaces for learning and working together, where people develop and implement solutions together; iii) rapid knowledge sharing, experimentation and prototyping: complex issues usually have more than one possible solution. Wherever possible, it (temporarily) tests new solutions in real life. This allows changes to become visible more quickly and their effects to be experienced.

Areas of Work

- Circular Economy
- Energy
- Environment/Climate Change
- Mobility
- Smart Cities & Regions
- Social Innovation & Inclusion
- Urban

Main Expertise

 Real-life Experimentation						
 User & Living Lab Research						

Adherent Member

Agrotopia Living Lab

Inagro VZW

Country: Belgium

www.inagro.be

Type of Living Lab:

- Living testbed
- Rural Living Lab
- Urban Living Lab
- Research driven Living Lab

To stimulate sustainable urban and greenhouse horticulture, further developments are required in using residual streams (heat, water, and CO2), recycling of resources, automatization, climatization and maximizing use of available space and energy efficiency. As the knowledge partner of agricultural and horticultural businesses in the areas of innovation and sustainability, Inagro tailors solutions to their needs. Inagro's new high tech research infrastructure to support the Living Lab is the 9000 sqm Agrotopia rooftop research greenhouse on top of the agricultural market in Roeselare. Six thousand sqm cultivation area, a compartment for multilayer indoor growing with artificial lighting and a 12 m high vertical compartment allow to co-create, develop, validate, and demonstrate innovative best practices for vegetable hydroponic systems. Agrotopia's location, at the agricultural auction market, where growers and

buyers meet daily, offers a unique opportunity towards interactions. It allows researchers, growers, technology providers, knowledge institutions, educators, and society to meet, collaborate, and co-create. To further stimulate this multidisciplinary approach, Agrotopia provides a unique platform to the Ghent University Agrotopia endowed chair, and the greenhouse is open to the growers and the general public. The Agrotopia Living Lab delivers the services to realize co-creation in this unique setting.

Areas of Work

- Agriculture & (Agri-)Food

Main Expertise

 Real-life Experimentation						
 User & Living Lab Research						

Adherent Member

Ghent Living Lab

City of Ghent

Country: Belgium

www.stad.gent/en

Type of Living Lab:

- Urban Living Lab
- Living testbed
- Living Lab as a service
- Research driven Living Lab

Ghent Living Lab focuses on the societal challenges relevant to the City of Ghent in Belgium. Focus areas of the City's Strategic Plan 'More than a Smart City' are Healthcare, Education and Climate transition. Ghent remains open to any other relevant new upcoming areas. Ghent Living Lab is the umbrella under which various innovation projects are initiated. It combines the creative forces of various partners from the quintuple helix, in an open collaborative network led by the City of Ghent. Ghent Living Lab draws on more than 10 years of experience of the City's work on innovative approaches to urban regeneration, including the use of digital technologies to support e-inclusion and e-participation. It works closely with the local research and innovation communities to take R&D out of the research labs and into real-world testbeds to create use-cases for future applications and services. The scope of this collaboration spans far beyond the Digitisation and ICT-related issues.

Areas of Work

- | | |
|---|------------------------------------|
| • Agriculture & (Agri-)Food | • Smart Cities & Regions |
| • AI and Emerging technologies | • SME & Start-ups |
| • Circular Economy | • Social Innovation & Inclusion |
| • Culture & Creativity (creative sectors) | • Urban |
| • Education and/or Vocational Training | • Zero Pollution & Decarbonization |
| • Energy | |
| • Environment/Climate Change | |
| • Health & Well Being | |
| • Industries & Manufacturing | |
| • Mobility | |

Main Expertise

 Real-life Experimentation						
 User & Living Lab Research						

Adherent Member

Happy Aging

In4care

Country: Belgium

<https://www.in4care.be/>

Type of Living Lab:

Living Lab as a service

Happy Aging is an integrated network and Living Lab for usercentred innovation in elderly care. It offers a real-life environment for companies and health care organizations to develop innovative concepts for elderly care. Besides being a real-life test environment, Happy Aging is also used to create new innovative ideas in co-creation with the elderly. This way it strengthens the effective implementation of these innovations. Happy Aging is a Living Lab consisting of many partners, each with their own expertise, including local authorities, care institutions, knowledge institutes, and companies. This ensures that the necessary expertise (quadruple helix) is present. The main purpose of the Happy Aging Living Lab is to develop innovative ideas, together with the elderly, to make sure that the elderly can reside longer and with a higher quality of life, in their home environment. The ideas that are developed within the Happy Aging Living Lab also contribute to a strong economic environment and job creation in the region.

Areas of Work

- AI and Emerging technologies
- Health & Well Being
- Mobility
- SME & Start-ups
- Social Innovation & Inclusion

Main Expertise

Adherent Member

ILVO Marine Living Lab

ILVO - Flanders Research Institute for Agriculture, Fisheries and Food

Country: Belgium

<https://ilvo.vlaanderen.be/en>

The Marine Living Lab strives for accelerated and sustainable innovation in the blue sectors. Concrete questions from these sectors are picked up and developed into a customized solution or project together with suitable partners. The living lab has expertise and a broad network in the fisheries, marine environment, marine production, marine biotechnology and the blue economy in general. ILVO's specialized labs, aquaculture facilities, experimental rooms and equipment, and access to research vessels, are available for the Marine Living Lab. With its 600 employees, advanced research infrastructure and extensive network of stakeholders, ILVO is interested to hear all your questions.

Effective Member

imec.livinglabs

IMEC

Country: Belgium

www.imec-int.com/en/livinglabs

Type of Living Lab:

Research driven Living Lab
Living Lab as a service

Imec offers researchers and entrepreneurs the chance to co-create and test their innovative solutions thoroughly with their target audience and stakeholders. The involvement of the end-users at an early stage of the development process makes it possible to tailor the innovation from the outset to real needs, habits, attitudes, and contextual factors. In that way products and services are better and have every chance of success on the market. The imec.livinglabs research includes users early on and all through the innovation process. This approach provides a solution to innovation thresholds and challenges such as: i) capturing, understanding, and validating users' interactions with products and services, at an early stage; ii) transforming ideas into prototypes users can interact within their daily context; iii) shaping '(minimum) viable products' through an iterative, agile process; iv) designing business models through stakeholder analysis and go-to-market definition.

Areas of Work

- AI and Emerging technologies
- Circular Economy
- Culture & Creativity (creative sectors)
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Energy
- Environment/Climate Change
- Health & Well Being
- Industries & Manufacturing
- Media
- Mobility
- Regulatory Learning
- Smart Cities & Regions
- SME & Start-ups
- Social Innovation & Inclusion
- Urban
- Water (Blue economy)
- Zero Pollution & Decarbonization

Main Expertise

- Business Model Innovation
- Co-creation Methods & Tools
- Governance Models
- Impact Assessments
- Implementation after Testing
- Innovation Strategies
- Living Lab Evaluation
- Panel Management
- Policy Making
- Real-life Experimentation
- Scaling-up
- Service Design
- Stakeholder Engagement
- User & Living Lab Research

Adherent Member

JF OCEANS

SENSO2ME NV

Country: Belgium

<https://senso2.me/en/>

Type of Living Lab:

Research driven Living Lab
Living Lab as a service

Senso2Me is a company based in Antwerp that produces technology and sells solutions to support the care of vulnerable persons in professional and residential environments. Senso2Me designs its own hardware, firmware, and cloud software to address market needs. Thanks to its innovative team, Senso2Me is able to follow and introduce novel technological and business opportunities to the market.

Areas of Work

- Environment/Climate Change
- Health & Well Being

Main Expertise

- Business Model Innovation
- Co-creation Methods & Tools
- Governance Models
- Impact Assessments
- Implementation after Testing
- Innovation Strategies
- Scaling-up
- Service Design
- Stakeholder Engagement
- User & Living Lab Research

Effective Member

Licalab - Living and Care Lab

Thomas More

Country: Belgium

www.licalab.be

Type of Living Lab:

Research driven Living Lab
Living Lab as a service
Living Lab testbed

LiCalab is a care living lab that supports businesses and organizations by including end users (citizens, patients, care professionals,...) from the very beginning of the development process until market introduction. LiCalab is a research group within Thomas More University of Applied Sciences. The Living Lab is strongly embedded in its region and has a large regional and international network on citizen, institutional, academic and policy level. The focus areas of LiCalab are medical care, (patient) rehabilitation, care technology, assisted living, active and healthy aging, and preventative healthcare. LiCalab gained extensive expertise in methodologies for co-creation, co-design, user experience, stakeholder engagement and participatory approaches and has experience in collaborating with Living Labs on an international scale.

Areas of Work

- AI and Emerging technologies
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Health & Well Being
- Policies
- Regulatory Learning
- SME & Start-ups
- Social Innovation & Inclusion
- Urban

Main Expertise

Business Model Innovation	Co-creation Methods & Tools	Governance Models	Innovation Strategies	Living Lab Evaluation	Policy Making	Real-life Experimentation
Scaling-up	Service Design	Stakeholder Engagement	User & Living Lab Research			

Adherent Member

Living Lab Animal Husbandry (LLAH)

ILVO - Flanders Research Institute for Agriculture, Fisheries and Food

Country: Belgium

<https://ilvo.vlaanderen.be/en>

Type of Living Lab:

Living Lab testbed
Rural Living Lab

The Living Lab Animal Husbandry (LLAH) is hosted by Flanders Research Institute for Agriculture, Fisheries and Food (ILVO). Main goal of the LLLAH is promoting practice-oriented innovation in the pig, cattle and poultry industry by co-creation, knowledge exchange and controlled experiments in research facilities and on commercial farms. Unique characteristics of the LLAH arise from its combination of translating research towards practical implementation and innovation by the farmers and industry. Within the LLAH the Pig Information Center, Cattle Information Center and Poultry Information Center act as an easily accessible contact, meeting, and communication platform in Flanders, providing information for all stakeholders, and bringing together and integrating the needs of the stakeholders into future practice-based and demand-driven research and co-creation. Enhancing transfer of both scientific and tacit knowledge towards and between all stakeholders is

essential for the competitiveness and sustainability of the Flemish livestock sector. The LLAH has access to pilot halls that are equipped with semi-industrial scale processing machines to develop innovations in the agri-food chain. Also test benches, an accredited plant diagnostic centre, equipment for precision farming, a seed reception and processing unit and accredited laboratories for feed, animal-end products, plants, soil, genetics are available. The infrastructure is used for own research, other private/research partners, and multi-partner research (projects).

Areas of Work

- Agriculture & (Agri-)Food
- Circular Economy
- Environment/Climate Change
- Rural
- Water (Blue economy)
- Zero Pollution & Decarbonization

Main Expertise

Co-creation Methods & Tools	Governance Models	Impact Assessments	Implementation after Testing	Innovation Strategies	Policy Making	Real-life Experimentation
Stakeholder Engagement	User & Living Lab Research					

Adherent Member

Living Lab Circulair

Inagro VZW

Country: Belgium

www.inagro.be

Type of Living Lab:

Rural Living Lab
Research driven Living Lab

The Living Lab Circular of Inagro is aimed for optimising the role of agriculture in the circular economy through increased co-creation. This is not limited to circular solutions between farms but also between farms, industry, and society. Relevant themes within agriculture are water, nutrients, biomass, and energy. Examples of previous projects are converting the fibres from the stems of brussels sprouts into paper or testing cleaned wastewater from food industry as an irrigation source for vegetables. Also, anaerobic digestors can convert manure or food waste into heat, energy and upgraded fertilisers. The LLC exists of a network of 20 stakeholder organisations from each party within the quadruple helix (society, industry, research, government). Furthermore, all pilot installations available at Inagro could be used for research at a practical relevant scale. This includes, but is not limited to, insect halls, aquaculture, anaerobic digester, greenhouses, climate rooms, harvesters, fertilisers, etc.

Areas of Work

- Agriculture & (Agri-)Food
- Circular Economy
- Energy
- Environment/Climate Change
- Research
- Rural
- Soil
- Water (Blue economy)

Main Expertise

 User & Living Lab Research						
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Adherent Member

Smart Retail City Lab

hub.brussels

Country: Belgium

www.smart-retail-city-lab.com

Type of Living Lab:

Urban Living Lab

A Smart Retail City is a city with a detailed knowledge of urban commerce, the customer, and trends. Initiated by Hub.brussels, the Smart Retail City Lab is a user-centred research and innovation project. Its objective is to lead the Brussels-Capital Region along the path of the Smart Retail City.

Areas of Work

- Smart Cities & Regions

Main Expertise

 Service Design						
 User & Living Lab Research						

Adherent Member

ZorgLab Aalst

Stadt Aalst

Country: Belgium

www.aalst.be/zorglab-aalst

Type of Living Lab:

Living Lab as a service

Zorglab Aalst is a living lab in health and care. It is an environment to test and experiment with innovative solutions in health and care. Zorglab Aalst supports and collaborates with entrepreneurs, researchers, policymakers and health care organizations in citizen-centered and/or patient-centred solutions. It provides advice, matchmaking of partners, co-creation and testing in real life. Zorglab Aalst makes a demonstration residence available in which the latest new applications, infrastructure and services can be demonstrated to the citizens/elderly/patients and care professionals themselves. The living lab is focusing on: Ageing in place, accessibility and adjusted housing; Age-friendly environments; Health & Care Tech; Prevention in health care; Collaboration in care and primary care.

Areas of Work

- Health & Well Being

Main Expertise

 Co-creation Methods & Tools	 Governance Models	 Impact Assessments	 Implementation after Testing	 Innovation Strategies	 Living Lab Evaluation	 Panel Management
 Policy Making	 Real-life Experimentation	 Scaling-up	 Service Design	 Stakeholder Engagement	 User & Living Lab Research	

BOSNIA & HERZEGOVINA

Adherent Member

Prijedor Circle Hub

PREDA (Development agency of the city of Prijedor)

Country: Bosnia & Herzegovina

www.prijedorhub.com

Prijedor Circle Hub is the first Living Lab operating in Bosnia and Herzegovina created and managed by PREDA, the Development Agency of the City of Prijedor in the Republika Srpska. PREDA has been the Lead partner in the Interreg Cross-border Cooperation 2014-2020 project entitled Creative@CBC, which has involved similar pathways leading to an application to the ENoLL three organizations from Bosnia and Herzegovina, Croatia and Montenegro. Within the process of preparation of the project proposal, as well as during its implementation, PREDA recognized that a number of previous projects managed throughout the past 5 years, which are reported herein, were clearly inspired by the Living Lab approach. The Prijedor Circle Hub belongs to PREDA and is supported by 16 institutions and organizations originating from the 4 communities of the quadruple-helix. Its functioning is mainly project-based, though this does not necessarily mean that all activities are financially covered by specific funding sources. In fact, the decision to create a Living Lab and apply to become an ENoLL member is part of a strategic decision and a long-term commitment to user-driven, open innovation as an instrument to create a fertile environment for business investments and the creation of new entrepreneurship in the area, which are the two main missions of PREDA as Development agency of the city of Prijedor.

BULGARIA

Adherent Member

SofiaLab

Sofia Development Association

Country: Bulgaria

www.sofia-da.eu

Type of Living Lab:

Urba Living Lab
Living Lab as a service
Living testbed
Research driven Living Lab

SofiaLab is an Urban Living Lab – a Smart City community infrastructure and ecosystem, promoting urban innovations and local development by bringing together leading actors from public administration, academia, industry, and social organisations. The unique feature of SofiaLab is that it is a means for the development and implementation of Sofia Smart Specialisation Strategy which has the concept of Smart City in the core. SofiaLab is the hub of many Living Lab nodes in the city. It aims to establish an experimentation and makerspace to motivate further piloting of digital innovations within the smart city context. SofiaLab aims to encourage bottom-up idea generation, open innovation, and value co-creation at the centre of its maker space for active experimentation and pilot testing. SofiaLab hosts countless events and social activities such as awareness campaigns, community workshops and trainings, hackathons, research and innovation, start-up acceleration, social events, digital technologies camps, venture capital related events, technology transfer and company matchmaking and others.

Areas of Work

- Circular Economy
- Culture & Creativity (creative sectors)
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Environment/Climate Change
- Regulatory Learning
- Smart Cities & Regions
- Social Innovation & Inclusion
- Urban
- Zero Pollution & Decarbonization

Main Expertise

 Living Lab Evaluation						
 User & Living Lab Research						

CANADA

Adherent Member

Llio - Living lab en innovation ouverte

Cegep de Rivière-du-Loup

Country: Canada

www.llio.quebec

Type of Living Lab:

Rural Living Lab
Research driven Living Lab

The Open Innovation Living Lab (LLio) is a centre for research and transfer of open innovative practices. Its mission is to facilitate the adoption of open innovation practices, in particular those involving users. The LLio's field is a research centre that intervenes in innovative social practices, both in the context of social and technological innovation. As its specialty concerns the adoption of open innovation practices, it explores, experiments, adapts, develops, and applies methods, devices, and tools such as Fab Lab, Design Thinking/Service Design, co-creation, empathy, serious games, and prototyping. LLio mainly uses the Living Lab approach to oversee the deployment of these tools and principles. The Centre does research and intervention in open innovation. To succeed in this transfer role, the LLio is interested in: i) OI practices, actors, spaces, and scales; ii) the capacity to innovate of people, organizations, and territories; iii) the evaluation of this capacity and its impact.

Areas of Work

- Agriculture & (Agri-)Food
- AI and Emerging Technologies
- Circular Economy
- Culture & Creativity (creative sectors)
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Energy
- Environment/Climate Change
- Health & Well Being
- Industries & Manufacturing
- Regulatory Learning
- Smart Cities & Regions
- SME & Start-ups
- Social Innovation & Inclusion
- Urban

Main Expertise

Adherent Member

Mandalab

Communautique

Country: Canada

www.communautique.quebec

Type of Living Lab:

Living Lab as a service
Research driven Living Lab

The Mandalab is a Living Lab network, hosted by Communautique. Communautique is a Montreal-based non-profit urban community network founded in 1995 to assist low-income individuals and families and other groups potentially excluded from participating in the information society. It provides Internet access and other ICT services and training throughout the province of Québec. In addition, Communautique has raised public awareness of the potential impact of provincial government online initiatives on the voluntary sector and the populations it serves. Communautique was invited to present its actions as part of the Quebec delegation to the World Summit on Information Society in Tunis. Communautique is also active in building ICT capacity within the voluntary sector itself to enable community groups to work more effectively to accomplish their goals. Communautique is actively involved in Industry Canada's Information Management/Information Technology (IM/IT) program, which aims to increase the technological capacity of the voluntary sector in Canada.

Areas of Work

- Culture & Creativity (creative sectors)
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Environment/Climate Change
- Social Innovation

Adherent Member

Rehabilitation Living Lab in the mall

Centre for Interdisciplinary Research in Rehabilitation of greater Montreal (CRIR)

Country: Canada

www.facebook.com/LaboratoireVivant

Type of Living Lab:

Research driven Living Lab

The Mandalab is a Living Lab network, hosted by Communautique. Communautique is a Montreal-based non-profit urban community network founded in 1995 to assist low-income individuals and families and other groups potentially excluded from participating in the information society. It provides Internet access and other ICT services and training throughout the province of Québec. In addition, Communautique has raised public awareness of the potential impact of provincial government online initiatives on the voluntary sector and the populations it serves. Communautique was invited to present its actions as part of the Quebec delegation to the World Summit on Information Society in Tunis. Communautique is also active in building ICT capacity within the voluntary sector itself to enable community groups to work more effectively to accomplish their goals. Communautique is actively involved in Industry Canada's Information Management/Information Technology (IM/IT) program, which aims to increase the technological capacity of the voluntary sector in Canada.

Areas of Work

- AI and Emerging Technologies
- Culture & Creativity (creative sectors)
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Health & Well Being
- Mobility
- Rural
- Social Innovation

CHINA

Adherent Member

Living Lab in Gerontechnology for Age-Friendly Home

Hong Kong Housing Society

Country: China

Type of Living Lab:

Urban Living Lab

Population ageing is a global phenomenon, yet it is unnecessarily degenerative but rather a human success on public health, medical advancements, economic and social development. Since 2010, both women and men in Hong Kong have led the world in life expectancy, currently standing at 88 and 82 years respectively. To embrace the challenges associated with the demographic transformation, we believe the key lies in age-friendly innovations and technologies. Being a “housing laboratory”, the Hong Kong Housing Society (HKHS) has pioneered various housing solutions in the past 70 years, and set up the Elderly Resources Centre (ERC) 17 years ago on foresight of the increasing ageing population to incubate innovative solutions and promote age-friendly home living to the community. Riding on the solid foundation of serving over 80,000 tenants and 20,000 of ERC visitors per year, the establishment of the HKHS Living Lab in Gerontechnology for Age-Friendly Home will play a significant role in materialising the co-creation process in collaboration with LL’s extensive network of stakeholders, end-users and developers.

Areas of Work

- Health & Well Being
- Smart Cities & Regions
- Social Innovation & Inclusion

Main Expertise

Co-creation Methods & Tools	Governance Models	Panel Management	Real-life Experimentation	Service Design	User & Living Lab Research

Adherent Member

Living Lab SHANGHAI

Tongji University

Country: China

LivingLab SHANGHAI is an educational platform based on the open approach and environment of the Sino-Finnish Centre, located at Tongji University. It promotes open innovation for generating social construction of knowledge, bridging top-down and bottom-up social innovation processes in real-world contexts by involving relevant stakeholders. Its main characteristics are: i) education-based research and practice: bridging the gaps between education, research and practice in the real world context; ii) design-driven application of new technology: a design-driven approach for complex social problems, involving a mix of human and societal needs where solutions employ new technology; iii) multi-stakeholder ecosystem: the ongoing development of eco-system consisting of enterprises, entrepreneurs, universities, research institutes, associations and other NGOs.

Adherent Member

Unisabana's Living Lab

Universidad de La Sabana

Country: Colombia

<https://livinglabsabana.com/tour/labs>

Type of Living Lab:

Research driven Living Lab

The Living Lab of Universidad de la Sabana is a concept of collective intelligence materialized in scenarios that integrate the academic, research, and social projection ecosystem centred on the territory and the people that are part of the region, acting as an organic co-creation platform and promoting applied knowledge through the generation of capacities in innovation and startups; the LL is a pioneer in the region and in Colombia, exploring new technologies to foster creation and creativity, seeking solutions to various challenges, promoting open innovation and developing prototypes to foster experiential learning. The management model of the LL is responsible for co-creation, prototyping, evaluation, and gamification processes, promoting active participation in specialized practical learning to develop new solutions, with a positive impact on the quadruple helix. Through new methodologies, tools, and technologies it contributes to the generation of new ecosystems of innovation.

Areas of Work

- AI and Emerging technologies
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Smart Cities & Regions
- Social Innovation & Inclusion

Main Expertise

Business Model Innovation

Co-creation Methods & Tools

Impact Assessments

Implementation after Testing

Innovation Strategies

Living Lab Evaluation

Real-life Experimentation

Stakeholder Engagement

User & Living Lab Research

COLOMBIA

Adherent Member

Pismo Hub

**Sisak Moslavina County
Development Agency for
encouraging economic
development, consulting
and representation (SI-
MO-RAItd)**

Country: Croatia

www.inkubator-pismo.eu

The initiative started as the Business Incubator Pismo Novska (focused on game development, AI, and blockchain technology) and later evolved into the first Living Lab in the Sisak-Moslavina County, and first to have the aim of using AI, gaming and blockchain technology solutions in digital transition and debureaucratization of public administration, which has been recognized as the County's major problem for years. Pismo Hub has established quality long-term relations with different groups of stakeholders (NGOs, government, academia, and private sector), given the type of business its host organization does as a regional development agency and due to its extensive network of business partners. The host organization is also a part of a number of renowned consortiums – Digital Innovation Hub DIGI SI DIH, Digital Innovation Hub Blockchain for Trusted Data Ecosystems, European Digital Innovation Hub for Smart Health, ARAGÓN DIH and other partnerships in this particular field. After the end of a pilot project in one local public administration unit, it is expected that other cities and municipalities will adopt the serious game and blockchain-based CRM program solutions in their own administration and city finances.

Adherent Member

Rijeka iLivingLab

University of Rijeka

Country: Croatia

www.pfri.uniri.hr/web/hr/index.php

**University of Rijeka,
Faculty of Maritime studies**

Rijeka iLivingLab most important capability is the possibility of research and innovation in interdisciplinary studies. Hosted at the Faculty of Maritime Studies, Rijeka iLivingLab, has access to persons involved in integrated and interdisciplinary research involving ICT, Maritime Transport, Logistics, International Trade Law, Maritime Economy and Engineering, as well as the implementation of new ICT learning technologies. iLivingLab consists of several labs mutually interconnected and mostly working together on different projects. Rijeka iLivingLab consists of 4 labs: Maritime, Logistics, e-learning and e-government labs. The oldest lab is Maritime Navigation, Safety and Security lab focusing on the development of safety and security procedures in maritime transport, as well as procedures for search and rescue at sea. The whole coastal part of the Republic of Croatia, in all its largeness, the full length of its 6,000-kilometre-long coast of Adriatic Sea and its thousand islands, represents a remarkable natural resource. The main concept of the Living Lab is the prevention of accidents at sea, including maritime terrorism as well as establishing a system of navigation, ship reporting system, complete coverage of the radio communication system, establishing a vessel control service in port areas and on the access routes to the ports of the largest passenger and cargo traffic volume, especially as regards dangerous cargoes, improving cooperation with corresponding offices and research activities in the neighbouring countries, namely in the Republic of Slovenia and the Republic of Italy, in applying the regulations of the system protecting the marine environment against pollution, and application of the Coast Zone Management principles.

Accepted to Grow

Danish organic on-farm living lab

Innovation Center for Organic Farming

Country: Denmark

<https://livinglabsabana.com/tour/labs>

Type of Living Lab:

Research driven Living Lab

The Danish Organic on-farm Living Lab (DKOFLL) is a national holistic network where there is the opportunity to experiment and bring into practice innovative solutions for organic farming. The DKOFLL works within three key areas: (1) building up and maintaining soil fertility; (2) develop efficient and resilient cropping systems; and (3) improve animal welfare. Each area covers a diverse portfolio of projects, stakeholders and farms, driving the development through specific measures and expertise.

As the manager organisation, the Innovation Centre for Organic Farming, has long experience in co-creation, setting up, running and funding activities within living labs located in organic farms, involving farmers, advisory services, universities, research institutes and local government as well as producers and retailers.

Areas of Work

- Agriculture & (Agri-)Food
- Environment/Climate Change

Main Expertise

Adherent Member

ENERGY & WATER - Greater Copenhagen Living Lab

City of Copenhagen

Country: Denmark

www.energiogvand.dk

Type of Living Lab:

Urban Living Lab
Living testbed

ENERGY & WATER – Greater Copenhagen Living Lab co-creates and tests tools for education, showcasing and citizen involvement that underpin the creation of sustainable city solutions. ENERGY & WATER is a collaboration between HOFOR (the largest utility company in Denmark) and the City of Copenhagen (the capital of Denmark).

Areas of Work

- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Energy
- Urban
- Water (Blue economy)
- Zero Pollution & Decarbonization

Main Expertise

Adherent Member

CODER Living Lab

LUT University

Country: Finland

Type of Living Lab:

Research driven Living Lab

CODER is an ICT-enabled Living Lab entirely dedicated to the innovation, development and validation of software systems, products and services with a human mind-set. It combines a physical smart environment that motivates open innovation, a cloud-based toolbox and equipment to develop and validate a wide range of user experience-centric software products, systems and services, as well as the large network of stakeholders and technology partners that provide the best business and technical competence and mentoring to the drivers of software technology innovation. The Lab aims to be

a place for effective and efficient engagement of a large pool of user communities and all stakeholders in all the stages of the software development and innovation lifecycle. CODER is the place for changing the human mind-set using software products, systems and services. The Lab is currently supporting research in the following areas: i) human-data interaction for data literacy; ii) participatory sensing and civic tech; iii) data and technology for ‘More-than-human’ and sustainable urban design; iv) smart cities; v) energy citizenship.

Areas of Work

- Agriculture & (Agri-)Food
- Circular Economy
- Culture & Creativity (creative sectors)
- Energy
- Environment/Climate Change
- Mobility
- Rural
- Smart Cities & Regions
- Social Innovation & Inclusion
- Urban
- Zero Pollution & Decarbonization

Main Expertise

 Scaling-up						
 User & Living Lab Research						

FINLAND

Innovation Partner

Finnish Network of Living Labs

Country: Finland

Type of Living Lab:

Network of Living Lab Operators

Finnish Network of Living Labs is a co-orchestrated platform of six Finnish universities of applied sciences. The platform originated at the time of the founding of ENoLL. The innovation partnership includes: Xamk South-Eastern Finland University of Applied Sciences, Haaga-Helia University of Applied Sciences, Savonia University of Applied Sciences, Centria University of Applied Sciences, Arcada University of Applied Sciences, and Häme University of Applied Sciences. The partnership embeds and develops Living Lab praxis with corporate and NGO partners in southern, eastern, and western Finland with the help of over 30 000 students and 3000 staff. The partnership is committed to: i) cooperation in national and international project planning and execution; ii) enhancing the international visibility of Finnish Living Labs; and iii) making an impact in the worldwide ENoLL community. Finnish Network of Living Labs is coordinated by Xamk. The network represents different types of Living Labs and is thus well-suited to explore best practices and exchange ideas, especially, about how to embed Living Lab methodology into local and regional development. The network operates through regular live co-learning forums which are open to international ENoLL partners in addition to online working groups.

Areas of Work

- Culture & Creativity (creative sectors)
- Health & Well Being
- Rural
- Smart Cities & Regions
- Other areas of work

Main Expertise

 Living Lab Evaluation						
 User & Living Lab Research						

FORUM VIRIUM HELSINKI

Adherent Member

Forum Virium Helsinki: Helsinki Innovation Districts

Forum Virium Helsinki

Country: Finland

<https://livinglabsabana.com/tour/labs>

Type of Living Lab:

Urban Living Lab

Forum Virium Helsinki, the city of Helsinki innovation company, co-creates urban futures with companies, universities, public sector, and residents. Its Living Labs include the Smart Kalasatama, Jätkäsaari Mobility Lab, and the Helsinki Innovation Districts.

The Helsinki Innovation Districts take the learnings from the Helsinki's Smart City District Kalasatama to the districts under regeneration. The work is based on experimentation with agile piloting programmes, co-creation of smart & green solutions and active resident engagement in the suburban districts.

Areas of Work

- AI and Emerging technologies
- Circular Economy
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Environment/Climate Change
- Health & Well Being
- Mobility
- Smart Cities & Regions
- Social Innovation & Inclusion

Main Expertise

 Living Lab Evaluation						
 User & Living Lab Research						

Adherent Member

Lahti Living Lab

LUT University

Country: Finland

www.lut.fi

Type of Living Lab:

Research driven Living Lab

The special focus of the Lahti Living Lab is to integrate the users into the innovation processes of public and private sector innovation and development focusing on all dimensions of sustainability and digitalization. For this purpose, methods and tools are developed and studied to fully enable knowledge creation and exploitation between users and professional developers. The methods of involving and activating the users vary, the encounters take place online but also face-to-face. Lahti Living Lab is implemented through research and development projects, which all have a common nominator, e.g. the users as active co-creators.

Areas of Work

- Circular Economy
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Environment/Climate Change
- Health & Well Being
- Mobility
- Policies
- Research
- Rural
- Social Innovation & Inclusion

Main Expertise

 Service Design						
 User & Living Lab Research						

Effective Member

Laurea Living Labs Network

Laurea University of Applied Sciences

Country: Finland

www.laurea.fi/en/research

LAUREA helps companies, public sector, academia, and citizens to co-create and pilot better innovations in various industrial domains. Living Lab provides professional know-how and education in Health and Wellbeing, Social Services, Correctional Services, Safety, Security and Risk Management, Business Management and Service Innovation, Circular Economy, Hospitality Management and Service Design, as well as Beauty and Cosmetics. LAUREA aims to make innovation more open, inclusive, and collaborative. Co-creation and experimentation do not happen without mediation. At LAUREA it is called 'orchestration'. LAUREA motivates businesses, researchers, public sector players and citizens to come together and innovate. Product development at the customer interface drastically reduces costs and time for launching. Collaboration with academia and businesses turns state-of-art research effectively into products and services. For citizens and public sector players, co-creation and innovation bring about better and more suitable services at reduced costs. Openness and free flow of information and ideas make processes more efficient and benefit all stakeholders. Adherence to open science, open innovation and open learning is LAUREA's competitive advantage. LAUREA's fields of expertise in RDI activities are holistic health and well-being, coherent security, service innovations and business models, entrepreneurship, and pedagogy.

Effective Member

TAMK Living Lab

Tampere University of Applied Sciences

Country: Finland

www.tuni.fi

Type of Living Lab:

Living testbed
Research driven Living Lab

TAMK Living Lab focuses on promoting health and wellbeing, business, and technology together with learning and creativity. In addition to the significant role as a higher education institution, TAMK conducts high-quality practical, cross-disciplinary research, development, and innovation projects jointly with all quadruple helix partners. These projects specifically emphasise the social, environmental, and economic impact on individuals, communities, and societies. One of the main focuses is profound expertise on human capacity development and training, especially in the fields of digital skills and competences. TAMK believes that young people are the best asset for the future. Talented students are integrated in Living Lab activities in many ways, collaborating closely with the public sector, companies, or other organizations, and innovatively solving their problems and challenges.

Areas of Work

- Agriculture & (Agri-)Food
- AI and Emerging technologies
- Circular Economy
- Culture & Creativity (creative sectors)
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Energy
- Environment/Climate Change
- Media
- Mobility
- Policies
- Regulatory Learning
- Research
- Rural
- Smart Cities & Regions
- SME & Start-ups
- Social Innovation & Inclusion
- Urban
- Water (Blue economy)
- Zero Pollution & Decarbonization

Main Expertise

 Panel Management						
 User & Living Lab Research						

FRANCE

Adherent Member

Brie'Nov

Brie'Nov

Country: France

www.brienov.fr

Type of Living Lab:

Rural Living Lab

Brie'Nov is an ecosystem of territorial and social innovation, both civic and digital. It is a melting pot that brings together various stakeholders (central place of the user). The Living Lab label encourages research, development, and collaboration. B'N promotes the challenge of digital as an opportunity for opening up and re-socializing. Brie'Nov is made up of entrepreneurs, local politicians, non-profit organizations, researchers, teachers and local residents. Main axes of work are based on a tripartite "bet" underpinning several projects: i) high-speed digital networks as a vector for overall development; ii) high-speed digital networks as a vector for opening up backwaters; iii) high-speed digital networks as a vector for social reintegration. Brie'Nov has also been labelled a Territory Factory (www.fabrique77.fr) and Territorial Pole of Economic Cooperation. These two national systems enable the Living Lab to accelerate various projects.

Areas of Work

- Circular Economy
- Culture & Creativity (creative sectors)
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Environment/Climate Change
- Mobility
- Rural
- Social Innovation & Inclusion

Main Expertise

Adherent Member

E2L Earth observation Living Labs

E2L Earth observation Living Labs

Country: France

www.e2l-coop.eu

Type of Living Lab:

Living testbed
Living Lab as a service
Research driven Living Lab

The aim of the cooperative society Earth observation Living Labs (E2L) is to develop the use of space technologies based on the tools of geospatial information, to serve rural territories, by co-designing innovative solutions to create value and to improve existing practices. The central idea of the Living Lab focuses on the concept of regional Living Labs: E2L proposes a set of contexts (ways of expressing requirements for users, testing and demonstrations), to prove the usefulness of the applications of research and development activities in space technologies. The aim of E2L is to support the creation of new services by placing the end user in the position of being a co-developer on the scale of publicly managed territories. E2L continues to develop the method initiated in the area of Pays Portes de Gascogne which has been the creation of a Pôle d'Expérimentation et d'Application des technologies spatiales – PATS (an experimentation cluster on the use of space

technologies). This cluster functions as an instrument enabling the adaptation of structural changes of the local economy to help emerging a new dynamic and competitive knowledge economy, based on the ability to experiment, on the local/regional scale. It supports research and technological development projects, whose strong potential of recovery depends on the transferability of its results to companies. Simultaneously, it encourages companies to enrol in the dynamics of research activities.

Areas of Work

- Agriculture & (Agri-)Food
- Energy
- Environment/Climate Change
- Rural
- Smart Cities & Regions
- Social Innovation & Inclusion
- Water (Blue economy)

Main Expertise

Adherent Member

Gérontopôle Nouvelle-Aquitaine

Gérontopôle Nouvelle-Aquitaine

Country: France

www.gerontopole-na.fr

Type of Living Lab:

Living Lab as a service

Gérontopôle Nouvelle-Aquitaine is a centre of expertise, support and action for active and healthy ageing well in the Nouvelle-Aquitaine region. It is a public organisation founded by the Regional Health Agency of Nouvelle-Aquitaine and the Nouvelle-Aquitaine Region, that brings together stakeholders for the active and healthy ageing: institutions; local authorities; research, training and innovation organisations; sanitary and social structures; user associations; businesses. It also works at EU level to exchange and develop responses to the demographic challenges. Thanks to its user-centred and cross-sectoral approach, it supports the development of services and devices with users and professionals. It aims at encouraging multidisciplinary research to improve the quality of life of older people, promoting local initiatives, innovating and supporting organisational, educational, professional and technological experiments and the development of local economy focused on ageing well.

Areas of Work

- AI and Emerging technologies
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Health & Well Being
- Mobility
- Policies
- SME & Start-ups
- Social Innovation & Inclusion
- Urban

Main Expertise

Adherent Member

HA&WB LL Healthy Aging & Well Being Gerontopole Auvergne

Gérontopôle Auvergne Rhône-Alpes (Gérontopôle AURA)

Country: France

The Healthy Ageing and Well-Being Living Lab (HA&WB LL) is supported by a non-profit organization the Gérontopôle Auvergne Rhône-Alpes (Gérontopôle AURA). The objective of the Healthy Ageing and Well-Being Living Lab is to explore and achieve, policies and business goals related to health, well-being and active ageing, as well as social inclusion of seniors. HA&WB Living Lab is established as a nucleus for open innovation activities and as a repository of relevant knowledge and expertise. It sets up, coordinates, facilitates and manages research using various settings.

Adherent Member

ICT Usage Lab

Centre Inria d'Université Côte d'Azur

Country: France

www.ictusagelab.fr

Type of Living Lab:

Living testbed
Living Lab as a service
Research driven Living Lab

ICT Usage Lab promotes multidisciplinary studies on usage-based innovation and coordinates researchers from different fields: artificial intelligence, computer science, data science, educational science, cognitive psychology and ergonomics, sociology, economics, etc. ICT Usage Lab aims at sharing its infrastructure (hardware, software, tools, etc.), as well as experiences and know-how. ICT Usage Lab is tackling challenges mainly in the field of digital science education: it aims at co-creating new educational materials in digital science with many involved actors (e.g. teachers, researchers, associations, entrepreneurs) to make people (children, pupils, students, citizens) understand the basics of computer science and to facilitate the dissemination of the digital science culture. The approach remains multidisciplinary and considers the latest research in innovative training, pedagogy and education. In parallel, the ICT Usage Lab also trains teachers in these new innovative teaching methods.

Areas of Work

- Agriculture & (Agri-)Food
- AI and Emerging technologies
- Culture & Creativity (creative sectors)
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Environment/Climate Change
- Health & Well Being
- SME & Start-ups
- Social Innovation & Inclusion

Main Expertise

Business Model Innovation	Co-creation Methods & Tools	Governance Models	Impact Assessments	Implementation after Testing	Innovation Strategies	Living Lab Evaluation
Panel Management	Real-life Experimentation	Scaling-up	Service Design	Stakeholder Engagement	User & Living Lab Research	

Adherent Member

La Fabrique du Futur

La Fabrique du Futur

Country: France

www.lafabriquedufutur.global

Type of Living Lab:

Living Lab as a service
Research driven Living Lab

The mission of La Fabrique du Futur is to help organisations (local authorities, companies, NGOs) to imagine and build desirable futures. The Living Lab promotes co-creation and collective intelligence. It is committed to "Techs for Good" approaches such as the use of 3D, virtual reality and metaverses. La Fabrique du Futur is promoting the concept of distributed Living Lab to accompany better the ongoing transitions needed by our planet.

Areas of Work

- AI and Emerging technologies
- Circular Economy
- Culture & Creativity (creative sectors)
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Smart Cities & Regions
- SME & Start-ups
- Social Innovation & Inclusion

Main Expertise

Business Model Innovation	Co-creation Methods & Tools	Governance Models	Impact Assessments	Implementation after Testing	Innovation Strategies	Living Lab Evaluation
Panel Management	Policy Making	Real-life Experimentation	Scaling-up	Service Design	Stakeholder Engagement	User & Living Lab Research

Adherent Member

Living Lab Saint Victor

Chu Amiens

Country: France

Type of Living Lab:

Living Lab as a service
Research driven Living Lab

Living Lab Saint Victor is situated In Amiens, France. Its easily accessible facilities and infrastructures are included in the University Hospital of Amiens and are adapted to conduct ecological studies in various living places, inpatients and outpatients wards. Living Lab Saint Victor objective is to be an efficient structure to test collaboratively from experimentation to use value, an idea, a technology or a solution and researches focused on technology for older adults and their caregivers. Living Lab Saint Victor provide expertise at different stages of the process. Living Lab aims to become a meeting place where actors from different disciplines, expertise and perspectives, will mutually enrich each other while collaborating together, and finally to attract investors and partners.

Areas of Work

- AI and Emerging technologies
- Health & Well Being
- Media
- Mobility
- Policies
- Regulatory Learning
- Smart Cities & Regions
- Social Innovation & Inclusion

Main Expertise

Co-creation Methods & Tools	Impact Assessments	Implementation after Testing	Innovation Strategies	Living Lab Evaluation	Policy Making	Real-life Experimentation
User & Living Lab Research						

Adherent Member

Lorraine Smart Cities Living Lab

Université de Lorraine - Laboratoire ERPI

Country: France

www.lf2l.fr/projects/lorraine-smart-cities-living-lab

Type of Living Lab:

Living Lab as a service
Living testbed
Urban Living Lab
Rural Living Lab
University Living Lab

Based on the universality of the university and its multidisciplinary, the Lorraine Smart Cities Living Lab (LSCLL) experiments in terms of projects, governance, and support platform since 2008. The LSCLL is a collaborative resource centre of the Université de Lorraine, to support and link the various thematic and territorial labs integrating users and implementing collaborative approaches in the service of research, development of innovations, training, and a citizen culture. ENOLL member since 2010 (4th wave), the LSCLL seeks to develop Public Private Population Partnerships (PPPPs) to disseminate innovation and related practices. Since 2014, the Lorraine Fab Living Lab® (LF2L) platform strengthens the Living Lab approach. This “innovation space” provides resources and 2D/3D/4D technologies allowing prospective assessment of innovative usages. The LSCLLL brings together several teams from the University of Lorraine. In 2018, INRAE Grand Est and AgroParisTech centre de Nancy joined the governance of the LSCLL as part of the national “Territories of Innovation” challenge with the “Des Hommes et des Arbres” project.

Areas of Work

- | | |
|--|------------------------------------|
| • AI and Emerging technologies | • Rural |
| • Circular Economy | • Smart Cities & Regions |
| • Education and/or Vocational Training | • SME & Start-ups |
| • Energy | • Social Innovation & Inclusion |
| • Environment/Climate Change | • Soil |
| • Health & Well Being | • Urban |
| • Industries & Manufacturing | • Zero Pollution & Decarbonization |
| • Policies | • Other areas of work |
| • Research | |

Main Expertise

Business Model Innovation	Co-creation Methods & Tools	Governance Models	Impact Assessments	Implementation after Testing	Innovation Strategies	Living Lab Evaluation
Panel Management	Policy Making	Real-life Experimentation	Scaling-up	Service Design	Stakeholder Engagement	User & Living Lab Research

Adherent Member

MedTechLab®

Ecole Nationale Supérieure des Mines de Saint Etienne (Ecole de l'Institut Mines-Télécom) & AESIO Santé

Country: France

www.aesio-sante.fr/medtechlab

Type of Living Lab:

Living Lab as a service
Living testbed
Research driven Living Lab

MedTechLab® is an interdisciplinary meeting space to think, to co-create, to model, to test, to experiment, and to assess the use of products and/or services incorporating new technologies in the fields of Health and Autonomy in a controlled environment and in a real-life environment. Human resources, areas and equipment are dedicated to MedTechLab®. MedTechLab® provides collective intelligent workshops based on Design Thinking methodology. In addition, MedTechLab® has a testbed consisting in a “smart apartment” equipped with different sensors (presence sensor/motion sensor) and cameras/analysers. The partnership between AESIO Santé and Mines - Saint Etienne is a major advantage. Engineers, scientists, students, and pedagogical engineers are available through the partnership with Ecole Nationale Supérieure des Mines de Saint-Etienne (Mines Saint-Etienne). Users and Health Professionals (general practitioners, medical specialists, healthcare assistants...) are available through the partnership with AESIO Santé. The testbed available in the Living Lab, MedTechLab®, is the opportunity to test products and/or services in a controlled environment. Experiments, in a real-life environment, are conducted in medico-social and health-care establishments.

Areas of Work

- AI and Emerging technologies
- Health & Well Being
- SME & Start-ups

Main Expertise

 Living Lab Evaluation						
 User & Living Lab Research						

Adherent Member

Nantes City Lab

Nantes Metropole

Country: France

www.metropole.nantes.fr/nantes-city-lab

Type of Living Lab:

Urban Living Lab

Through the Nantes City Lab, Nantes Métropole provides a range of experimental sites, equipment, data, and engineering services to test innovative solutions in situ, in vivo, at scale 1. Nantes City Lab is a system dedicated to full-scale experimentation of innovative solutions by start-ups, SMEs, large groups, researchers, universities, and associations. It brings together concrete means to innovate in the Nantes metropolitan area, including:

- An urban laboratory: places and equipment to test innovative solutions related to social, ecological, and economic transitions.
- A service to facilitate innovation through experimentation: a single point of contact, labelling, research for places to experiment, links with Nantes Métropole technical departments, search for partnerships, definition of citizen interactions adapted to the projects, monitoring of experimentation, evaluation, and promotion.

Areas of Work

- Circular Economy
- Energy
- Environment/Climate Change
- Health & Well Being
- Mobility
- Smart Cities & Regions
- Social Innovation & Inclusion
- Urban
- Zero Pollution & Decarbonization

Main Expertise

 Stakeholder Engagement						
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Adherent Member

Normandy Living Lab

Pôle TES

Country: France

www.pole-tes.com

Type of Living Lab:

Living testbed

Normandy Living Lab's focus is on the efficient development of innovative products and services in the fields of digital agriculture, industry, health, smart territories, and creative digital content, by systematically placing the product or service user at the heart of the innovation process. Thanks to its wide variety of members and its continuous work with local authorities and communities, NLL is building a life-size testing environment covering all of Normandy. That way, it aims at being a vector for the co-creation of digital innovations, between designers and end-users, for a wide number of economic sectors.

Adherent Member

Pasteur Innovative Living Lab of Nice

CNR Santé (National Reference Centre for Homecare and Independent Living)

Country: France

Created in 2009 by the French Ministry of the Economy, Industry and Employment, the CNR Santé (National Reference Centre for Homecare and Independent Living) is an association that brings together a large number of stakeholders focused on healthcare innovation. As part of the portfolio of CNR offerings, "PAILLON 2020" Living Lab fosters the emergence and growth of digital technologies in the domain of Homecare and Independent Living. The Healthcare Innovation Center that hosts the Living Lab was launched in 2015 and is co-run by the Healthcare Directorate and the Nice Metropolis. The aim of the Healthcare Innovation Center is to establish an ecosystem of innovative companies, researchers and institutions focused on the field of ageing, autonomy, digital healthcare, as well as social innovations in health. Living Lab PAILLON 2020 located in close proximity to the newest hospital in Nice (Hôpital Pasteur 2) and is geared for evaluation, discovery and uptake of innovative healthcare technologies, in particular, devices used by patients in their homes. The Living Lab is equipped with a model apartment that is designed as a showcase and a testing platform for technologies supporting independent living and autonomy.

Areas of Work

- Agriculture & (Agri-)Food
- AI and Emerging technologies
- Circular Economy
- Culture & Creativity (creative sectors)
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Energy
- Health & Well Being
- Industries & Manufacturing
- Media
- Mobility
- Rural
- Smart Cities & Regions
- SME & Start-ups
- Urban

Main Expertise

 Living Lab Evaluation							
 User & Living Lab Research							

Adherent Member

Smart City Living Lab

Dédale

Country: France

www.dedale.info/_objets/medias/autres/rosalab-tract-a5-sept2021-ecran-1223.pdf

Type of Living Lab:

Urban Living Lab

The SmartCity Living Lab invites creative people, companies, researchers, and urban planners to come and test in situ and in vivo innovative solutions and services. The main themes of the SmartCity Living Lab are public space, circular economy, sustainable city, zero carbon, mobility, urban agriculture, citizen participation, smart city, sport and culture. The SmartCity Living Lab is financed by the Region (PICRI), the Ministry of Culture, and Europe (eContent+). It has enabled the implementation of experiments in the heart of the campus of the Cité Internationale Universitaire and has laid the foundations of the first urban Living Lab in Paris: i) these experiments accompany the territorial development and urban projects of the Greater Paris region and take the form of pilots and prototypes involving local actors, users, and inhabitants of the concerned territories; ii) these experiments have led to the development of digital tools in the context of participatory approaches involving the inhabitants and users of Paris and the southern suburbs and allowed Dédale to initiate Domaine Public, a research and experimentation programme on public space.

Areas of Work

- Circular Economy
- Culture & Creativity (creative sectors)
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Environment/Climate Change
- Mobility
- Smart Cities & Regions
- Social Innovation & Inclusion
- Urban

Main Expertise

 Panel Management						
 User & Living Lab Research						

Adherent Member

UDD - Université du Domicile

IPERIA l'Institut

Country: France

www.iperia.eu

UDD is hosted by Iperia l'Institut, an association which has been contributing to the professionalization of domestic work for more than 20 years by providing training and certification. UDD works in the field of well-being and social innovation. UDD focuses on skills&home. UDD explores the invisible practices, activities, and skills, that are developed at home and that people do unconsciously. Living Lab's main goal is to offer value, and to co-create trainings, products, services and good practices, to give people solutions to benefit from all of them. This will also enable the professionalization of domestic abilities. The UDD has the capabilities to create user-centred solutions to help people to live better at home.

Adherent Member

Universcience Living Lab

Etablissement Public
Palais de la Découverte
Cité des sciences et de l'industrie

Country: France

www.cite-sciences.fr/fr/au-programme/lieux-ressources/carrefour-numerique2

Type of Living Lab:

Urban Living Lab
Living Lab as a service
Research driven Living Lab

Universcience merges two Parisian science centres: i) the “Palais de la Découverte”; and ii) “la Cité des sciences et de l’industrie”. Its simple yet challenging goal is to inspire as many people as possible to be curious about the world around them, encouraging them both to marvel at science and to engage in scientific reasoning. Universcience provides: i) exhibitions accessible to all; ii) conferences, debates, events, publications; iii) spaces designed specifically for children (Cité des enfants); iv) dedicated services at the “Cité des métiers” and “Cité de la santé”; v) documentary resources with the Science Library; vi) experiments with innovative tools such as the FabLab and the Living Lab at the Carrefour numérique.

Universcience Living Lab welcomes and supports innovative projects in the fields of education, culture, entrepreneurship, social innovation and digital technologies. Visitors are involved as co-designers in the research or innovation process, influencing and bringing added value to the project.

Areas of Work

- AI and Emerging technologies
- Culture & Creativity (creative sectors)
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- SME & Start-ups
- Social Innovation & Inclusion
- Urban
- Other areas of work

Main Expertise

 User & Living Lab Research						
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GERMANY

Innovation Partner

Collaborating Centre on Sustainable Consumption and Production

Collaborating Centre on Sustainable Consumption and Production

Country: Germany

<https://www.cscp.org>

The CSCP (Collaborating Centre on Sustainable Consumption and Production) is an international, non-profit think and do tank. Together with companies, political organisations and civil society actors, the CSCP pursues its mission to mainstream sustainability towards enabling the good life for all. The focus of the Centre is on enabling sustainable consumption and production patterns. With its collaborative approach, the CSCP accelerates change based on the special expertise of the Centre in the following areas: Lifestyles & Behaviour, Infrastructure, Products & Services, Business & Entrepreneurship and Policy. Within these areas, the centre works as a think and do tank, specialised in collaborating with diverse organisations around the globe and across sectors. Together they work on the vision of a good life by identifying, developing and scaling transformative solutions.

Areas of Work

- Agriculture & (Agri-)Food
- AI and Emerging technologies
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Energy
- Health & Well Being
- Industries & Manufacturing
- Mobility
- Rural
- Smart Cities & Regions
- SME & Start-ups
- Social Innovation & Inclusion
- Urban
- Water (Blue economy)
- Zero Pollution & Decarbonization
- Other areas of work

K8

Adherent Member

K8 Institut fuer strategische Aesthetik gGmbH
K8

Country: Germany

www.k8.design/k8-english

Type of Living Lab:

Living testbed
Urban Living Lab
Living Lab as a service
Research driven Living Lab

As a “transformation organization”, K8 focuses on cross-sector involvement in processes of change. Transformation is understood as a combination of 5 fields of action. At the center of all transformation processes are people acting individually and collectively. K8 therefore explores and develops complementary forms of collective, public, data-based, value-creating and sustainable action. Each field of action can become the lead dimension (depending on the context), and the other focal points can then be used to identify concrete options for action. Because they focus on different social contexts, these fields of action also refer to complementary dimensions of social impact.

Areas of Work

- AI and Emerging technologies
- Circular Economy
- Culture & Creativity (creative sectors)
- Health & Well Being
- Media
- Mobility
- Policies
- Regulatory Learning
- Smart Cities & Regions
- SME & Start-ups
- Social Innovation & Inclusion

Main Expertise

Adherent Member

Living Labs Incubator

RWTH Aachen University

Country: Germany

www.humtec.rwth-aachen.de/LLI

Type of Living Lab:

Research driven Living Lab

Living Labs Incubator (LLI) studies and supports the work of Living Labs at and around RWTH Aachen University, the largest technical university in Germany. The main goals of the LLI are: establishing a network of Living Labs, developing adequate Living Lab research and evaluation methods and standards, support Living Lab research and practice in the LL Training Centre. Facing up to global sustainability challenges in a region with deep structural changes, the LLI seeks to strengthen the local, regional and national innovation ecosystem that the RWTH Aachen University forms an integral part of. By facilitating peer-learning, offering methods and tools and reflecting on political and epistemic dimensions, the LLI provides a unique knowledge platform devoted to research in and through Living Labs based at a technical university. LLI is funded within the Excellence Strategy by the German state and federal governments, aiming at promoting cutting-edge inter- and transdisciplinary research.

Areas of Work

- Agriculture & (Agri-)Food
- AI and Emerging technologies
- Circular Economy
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Energy
- Environment/Climate Change
- Gender
- Health & Well Being
- Industries & Manufacturing
- Mobility
- Regulatory Learning
- Research
- Smart Cities & Regions
- SME & Start-ups
- Social Innovation & Inclusion
- Soil
- Urban
- Water (Blue economy)
- Zero Pollution & Decarbonization

Main Expertise

Adherent Member

SmartFactoryOWL

Fraunhofer IOSB-INA

Country: Germany

www.smartfactory-owl.de

Type of Living Lab:

Living testbed

The SmartFactoryOWL is the real lab for industry 4.0 in Ostwestfalen-Lippe and offers companies and research institutions extensive possibilities and services for the co-creation of the factory of the future. The joint institution of the Fraunhofer IOSB-INA and the OWL University of Applied Sciences in Lemgo follows the three pillars: research, qualification, and transfer of technologies of the digital industry. In these three fields, SmartFactoryOWL provides answers to many questions and inspiration for your own development, demonstrating it in a worldwide unique Industry 4.0 infrastructure. What do you find there? On highly attractive research, production, and seminar areas, SmartFactoryOWL informs you about research results in the areas of digital transformation of the industry, future of work and process optimization. On 2000 sqm production and innovation area, technologies are presented in a way that you can experience their benefits first hand. SmartFactoryOWL helps companies to identify fields of action in the transfer of knowledge and technology and in the implementation of projects by matching them with experts in a suitable way.

Areas of Work

- AI and Emerging technologies
- Circular Economy
- Energy
- Industries & Manufacturing
- SME & Start-ups

Main Expertise

Adherent Member

Internet of Food Alliance (InoFA)

INTERNET OF FOOD ALLIANCE SUPPORT OFFICE IKE

Country: Greece

<https://inofa.gr/>

Type of Living Lab:

Living testbed
Rural Living Lab

Founded in 2022, InoFA operates on the premise that Digital Technology will dominate the European agrifood value chain. A vertically integrated cluster, funded by the Greek General Secretariat for Research and Innovation, has been formed around an IoT connectivity framework encompassing LoRa telecommunications, cloud services, and remote agronomic consultancy. This cluster comprises farmers, packers, retailers, service providers, technology firms, RTOs, and civil society groups. Geographically spanning Greece, it covers plant and animal production as well as services. Aligned with the EU's Green Deal policy and member entities' practical needs, InoFA designs eco-conscious projects, supplying tools like biostimulants and compostable ground covers. Simultaneously, digital traceability uplifts farmers' visibility, aiding successful transitions.

Areas of Work

- Agriculture & (Agri-)Food
- Circular Economy
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Rural

Main Expertise

 Real-life Experimentation						
 Stakeholder Engagement						

GREECE

Accepted to Grow

Just Transition Living Lab

University of Western Macedonia

Country: Greece

“Just Transition” is an ecosystem sharing the same vision and implementing a process, based on structured and constructive dialogue and an agenda shared with citizens, workers, industry, enterprises, governments and academia, that need to be further elaborated and explored in geographical, economic, political, cultural, and social context. JTLL is an educational, collaborative, research and innovation living lab, created as a public-private partnership to tackle the Just Transition challenges at the respective areas around the globe. The Just Transition Institute Greece (JTIG), together with the University of Western Macedonia (UoWM), as well as other institutions adopting our dream for a just future, connect citizens, enterprises and policy makers of areas in transition, who face the greatest challenges of their modern history in our area.”

Accepted to Grow

**KAEM Living Lab
American Farm School – Innovation and Impact HUB**

Country: Greece

www.afs.edu.gr

Type of Living Lab:

Rural Living Lab

KAEM LL highlights the deep connection between olive trees, olive oil and environmental sustainability and cultural heritage. Educating consumers about their purchases and promoting responsible consumption is a key objective. It also aims to develop olive tourism and gastronomy as high-value offerings, marketing olive products as premium goods. Navigating legal frameworks, health assertions, and certifications, it ensures compliance and trust in olive products. A holistic, olive-centric system is proposed, integrating all aspects of olive production and consumption. The educational component focuses on fostering skills development and entrepreneurship within the olive industry, as well as improving transportation and processing techniques to enhance efficiency and product quality. This comprehensive approach aims to create a sustainable, culturally rich, and economically viable olive industry.

Areas of Work

- Agriculture & (Agri-)Food
- Environment/Climate Change
- Rural

Main Expertise

Adherent Member

Mediterranean Soil Living Lab (MACCSOIL)

Mediterranean Agrofood Competence Center

Country: Greece

<https://macc.gr/en/macc-soil/>

Type of Living Lab:

Living testbed
Living Lab as a service
Urban Living Lab
Rural Living Lab

The Mediterranean Soil Living Lab (MACCSOIL LL) embodies a visionary quest towards redefining the future of agriculture through the prism of soil sustainability. MACCSOIL LL invites living labs, Scientists and Communities, worldwide to join in a groundbreaking journey to unearth sustainable practices that safeguard our planet's very foundation, its - soil. This dynamic platform it's a movement towards harmonizing agricultural productivity with environmental stewardship. Through fostering a vibrant community of researchers, farmers, and eco-conscious innovators, MACC Soil LL is crafting a narrative where soil health is central to address global challenges of climate change and food security. It's an open invitation for living labs globally to collaborate, share insights, and co-create solutions that resonate with the urgent need for sustainability. At the heart of the MACC Soil LL mission lies an inspiring vision: to transform soil into a living testament of resilience and prosperity.

Areas of Work

- Agriculture & (Agri-)Food
- AI and Emerging technologies
- Circular Economy
- Culture & Creativity (creative sectors)
- Energy
- Environment/Climate Change
- Health & Well Being
- Regulatory Learning
- Smart Cities & Regions
- SME & Start-ups
- Urban

Main Expertise

Adherent Member

SMART Living Lab

University of Western Macedonia (UOWM), Department of Electrical and Computer Engineering

Country: Greece

<https://smart.ece.uowm.gr>

Type of Living Lab:

Living testbed
Living Lab as a service
Research driven Living Lab

SMART is a Living Lab (LL) designed to act as a user-centric open innovation ecosystem attached to the value potential of new markets. The facilities of University of Western Macedonia and residential prosumers in the district of Central and Western Macedonia in Greece compose the real testing environment. SMART aims to balance the public action considering the generality of citizens' concern through the active participation of users. The different climate conditions and geographical particularities of the users allow a wide range of real-life testing, including actors with little economic weight. The team of SMART LL, consisting of Professors, post-doc researchers, PhD candidates and engineers, aims to create strong ties between the academia and the local business infrastructure with special focus on SMEs. SMART is based on the pillars of research, education and industrial testing. Through the educational dimension, the students can have access to records and assets of actual users.

Areas of Work

- Energy
- Environment/Climate Change
- Research
- Rural
- Smart Cities & Regions
- SME & Start-ups
- Zero Pollution & Decarbonization

Main Expertise

Effective Member

Thessaloniki Action for Health & Wellbeing Living Lab

Medical Physics & Digital Innovation Lab - School of Medicine, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki

Country: Greece

<https://imedphys.med.auth.gr/>

Type of Living Lab:

Living testbed
Research driven Living Lab

Thess-AHALL, active since 2014, is a unique research and innovation hub in Thessaloniki. It promotes regional development and sustainable health technologies, focusing on physical, mental, and social health, active and healthy ageing, and quality of life. It co-creates technological solutions to ease independent living, improve conditions for older adults, chronic patients, and vulnerable populations, and empower the healthcare workforce. Powered and governed by the Lab of Medical Physics & Digital Innovation of the Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (AUTH), it has engaged in citizen science and participatory research with AUTH and other local entities. Since spring 2022, it has relaunched its activities, forming a coalition with a holistic approach to health and wellbeing, focused on oncology research, agri-food, urban resilience, environmental change, and cultural sectors. Thess-AHALL transformed Thessaloniki into an urban living lab, addressing societal and health challenges.

Areas of Work

- Agriculture & (Agri-)Food
- AI and Emerging technologies
- Culture & Creativity (creative sectors)
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Environment/Climate Change
- Health & Well Being
- Media
- Smart Cities & Regions
- Social Innovation & Inclusion
- Urban

Main Expertise

Business Model Innovation	Co-creation Methods & Tools	Impact Assessments	Implementation after Testing	Innovation Strategies	Living Lab Evaluation	Panel Management
Real-life Experimentation	Service Design	Stakeholder Engagement	User & Living Lab Research			

Effective Member

Thessaloniki Smart Mobility Living Lab

Medical Physics & Centre for Research and Technology Hellas - Hellenic Institute of Transport (CERTH - HIT)

Country: Greece

www.smartmlab.imet.gr

Type of Living Lab:

Urban Living Lab

Thessaloniki Smart Mobility Living Lab is one of Europe's largest Living Labs on mobility. The entire city of Thessaloniki is a platform for testing technological and innovative solutions for shared and on-demand mobility, cooperative and autonomous vehicles and will soon be extended to freight transport. Thessaloniki is in the list of smart cities in the mobility sector, and this would not have been possible without the involvement of the bodies that make up the ecosystem of the city, which has been created over the last decade and is constantly growing. In this ecosystem, various mobility operators and technology providers are engaged in providing data and expertise to create the right conditions for the exploitation of this infrastructure for the benefit of the whole ecosystem, which has the citizens at its center. The Thessaloniki Smart Mobility Living Lab includes, among others: i) extended IoT equipment in vehicles (bikes, e-scooters, taxis and trains) and in the city streets (Bluetooth detectors, cameras, radars); ii) real time traffic data in the whole Region of Central Macedonia (including travel time along pre-defined routes and traffic speed in road segments); iii) short-term predictions of traffic conditions and travel time based on multi-source data; iv) mobility and activity patterns extraction and analysis.

Areas of Work

- Mobility
- Smart Cities & Regions
- SME & Start-ups
- Social Innovation & Inclusion
- Urban
- Zero Pollution & Decarbonization

Main Expertise

Business Model Innovation	Co-creation Methods & Tools	Governance Models	Impact Assessments	Implementation after Testing	Innovation Strategies	Living Lab Evaluation
Panel Management	Policy Making	Real-life Experimentation	Scaling-up	Service Design	Stakeholder Engagement	User & Living Lab Research

Adherent Member

Discovery Agricultural On-farm and Research Living Lab

Discovery Center Nonprofit Ltd.

Country: Hungary

<https://discoverycenter.eu/>

Type of Living Lab:

Rural Living Lab
Research driven Living Lab

Discovery LL has been an operational living lab since 2019, with an established network of stakeholders, including a group of active end users. Our activities and connections are well-established nationwide; we are financially independent and have access to manage thousands of hectares for our real-life experiments across Hungary, which have had significant impacts in the past 3 years since operations began. Host-staff members are qualified and experienced in their respective fields and are motivated to keep our stakeholders actively involved in the process of unravelling possible improvements for more resilient agricultural practices as extreme conditions increase.

The main goal of our living lab is to become a leading research network and location for sustainable soil management and precision agriculture, covering the main environmental conditions of the Carpathian basin. The LL aims to engage users from different stakeholder groups through its inclusive operation to gather research ideas and maintain credibility through well-defined and documented methods and activities.

Areas of Work

- Agriculture & (Agri-)Food
- Research
- Rural
- Soil

Main Expertise

 Real-life Experimentation						
 User & Living Lab Research						

HUNGARY

Adherent Member

Grow Stars Institute Living Lab

Csillagváros Kft.

Country: Hungary

<https://www.csillagvaros.com/#gsill>

Type of Living Lab:

Urban Living Lab
Living testbed
Research driven Living Lab

Grow Stars Institute Living Lab (GSILL) is a multiple site Controlled Environment Agriculture (CEA) facility with professional R&D&I staff capable of planning, executing, and evaluating complex research & innovation on every field of vertical farming, urban farming, and healthy food production. Established in 2021 using the latest state-of-the-art technologies, represents today an ideal connection between R&D and industrial environments. The LL provides a unique and well-developed infrastructure in every field of CEA and contains 5 individually controllable vertical farm systems in separate rooms, and 3 small scale growth cabinets. In GSILL the users are involved in every step of the innovation process to co-create innovative products, services, systems or processes for urban farming, vertical farming and food safety. GSILL introduced its unique Vertical Farm as a Service (VFaaS) solution for stakeholders from the academic, governmental, public, and civil sectors.

Areas of Work

- Agriculture & (Agri-)Food
- AI and Emerging technologies
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Health & Well Being
- Rural
- SME & Start-ups
- Urban

Main Expertise

Effective Member

ÖMKI On-farm Living Lab

Hungarian Research Institute of Organic Agriculture

Country: Hungary

www.biokutatas.hu

Type of Living Lab:

Research driven Living Lab

ÖMKI's On-farm Living Lab is an agroecology-focused nationwide participatory experimentation network which includes a variety of field trials and technology tests co-designed and co-implemented with farmers in Hungary, with the aim to promote agro-ecological transition. It works since 2012 in the field of arable crops, horticulture, viticulture, apiculture, and since 2020 also animal husbandry. In frame of the On-farm Living Lab, the Living Lab tests in different sub-networks how new products, practices and technological innovations perform under the diversity of everyday farming. Participating farmers gain feedback directly from their own production experiences, land, and technology creating space for open innovation and dynamic knowledge co-creation between farmers, researchers, and other stakeholders of the value chains. At the same time, the results give a broader picture of Hungarian organic and agroecological production practices and locally applicable solutions.

Areas of Work

- Agriculture & (Agri-)Food

Main Expertise

Adherent Member

Well-being Living Lab Nagykovacsi

TREBAG Intellectual property- and Project Manager Ltd

Country: Hungary

www.trebag.hu

Type of Living Lab:

Rural Living Lab
Living Lab as a service
Research driven Living Lab

The mission of the Well-being Living Lab Nagykovacsi is to carry out and participate in R&D activities that can be used to improve people's well-being and quality of life in many areas of life. Its mission is to develop, deliver, apply and disseminate new services and methods (e.g. through education) using the results of R&D activities.

Areas of Work

- Agriculture & (Agri-)Food
- Culture & Creativity (creative sectors)
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Environment/Climate Change
- Health & Well Being
- Industries & Manufacturing
- Rural
- SME & Start-ups
- Social Innovation & Inclusion

Main Expertise

A row of seven icons representing different expertise areas: a bar chart for Business Model Innovation, two hands holding a gear for Co-creation Methods & Tools, a checklist for Impact Assessments, a lightbulb and gear for Implementation after Testing, a gear for Innovation Strategies, two hands holding a heart for Living Lab Evaluation, and a hand holding a tool for Service Design.

Business Model Innovation Co-creation Methods & Tools Impact Assessments Implementation after Testing Innovation Strategies Living Lab Evaluation Service Design

An icon showing a person and a gear.

User & Living Lab Research

IRELAND

Adherent Member

Atlantic Innovation Region

Western Development Commission

Country: Ireland

www.westerndevelopment.ie

Type of Living Lab:

Living Lab as a service
Living testbed
Research driven Living Lab

The WDC's remit covers the seven counties primarily on the Atlantic coast of Ireland: Donegal, Leitrim, Sligo, Roscommon, Mayo, Galway, and Clare. Its strategic themes for 2019-2024 are: i) Regional Promotion, ii) Regional Leadership, and iii) Sustainable Enterprise. The WDC's role is that of an Orchestrator that enables this region to stimulate new social/business, innovations, partnerships, initiate experiments, and Living Labs, and foster a vibrant ecosystem across the region with global links and recognition. The most important characteristic of the AIR Living lab is the network it creates for multiple actors to come together to test innovative solutions to societal problems. Using a quadruple helix approach, the Lab acts as an orchestrator to bring together cross-cutting competencies in creativity, data, sensors, and mobility to tackle emerging challenges in vertical industries such as healthcare, energy generation, and transport. Network allows the actors to work with industry, Academia

and civic society in a way that combines local knowledge and sectoral expertise to identify challenges and to source partners to solve these challenges. The Lab is also linked to the WDC Investment Fund, providing a path to scaling for successful start-up ideas that emerge from experiments. Furthermore, because the Lab is virtual, it is scalable, builds on existing resources and does not compete with existing actors but complements them and develops synergies.

Areas of Work

- AI and Emerging technologies
- Energy
- Health & Well Being
- Mobility
- Smart Cities & Regions
- SME & Start-ups
- Social Innovation & Inclusion

Main Expertise

Business Model Innovation, Co-creation Methods & Tools, Governance Models, Innovation Strategies, Living Lab Evaluation, Policy Making, Real-life Experimentation, Stakeholder Engagement, User & Living Lab Research

Adherent Member

Citizen Innovation Lab

University of Limerick & Limerick City & County Council

Country: Ireland

www.citizeninnovationlab.ie

Type of Living Lab:

Urban Living Lab

Limerick's Citizen Innovation Lab is a place for observation, co-creation and experimentation in the city. It is a collaboration between the University of Limerick, Limerick City and County Council, and the citizens of Limerick, supporting them to work together on a sustainable future for the city. It is a place where people can help shape a path to a climate neutral Limerick by 2050. As a living lab, it leads and supports collaborative research projects, citizen-led initiatives, digital and citizen science tools, and public engagement activities. The shared approach focuses on areas including decarbonisation, the clean energy transition, climate innovation, digitisation and technology, active travel, and urban development. The Citizen Innovation Lab puts people at the heart of Limerick's climate transition.

Areas of Work

- Culture & Creativity (creative sectors)
- Energy
- Environment/Climate Change
- Mobility
- Policies
- Regulatory Learning
- Research
- Smart Cities & Regions
- Social Innovation & Inclusion
- Urban
- Zero Pollution & Decarbonization

Main Expertise

Business Model Innovation, Co-creation Methods & Tools, Implementation after Testing, Innovation Strategies, Living Lab Evaluation, Panel Management, Policy Making, Real-life Experimentation, Scaling-up, Service Design, Stakeholder Engagement, User & Living Lab Research

Adherent Member

Dingle Peninsula

Dingle Hub

Country: Ireland

www.dinglehub.com

Type of Living Lab:

Rural Living Lab
Living testbed

The vision of Dingle Hub is to build a creative, liveable, and sustainable community, fostering a vibrant and diverse ecosystem of stakeholders to facilitate the creation and maintenance of well-paid, year-round incomes on the Dingle Peninsula. Dingle Peninsula Living Lab has developed an innovative model of Remote Regional Development. It balances highly structured focus, anchored in core pillars, with a flexibility of delivery across processes and partnerships. It builds on existing assets and continuously shares outputs and learnings. Dingle Peninsula Living Lab applies a flexible multi-layered approach building on the local; attracting the new, building networks of resources and capabilities aspiring to, primed

for and delivering entrepreneurial growth of sustainable enterprise (private and social). Engagement at all levels – community, research, industry, and policymaker – is central to this story and has led to a hybrid top-down meets bottom-up approach that is achieving concrete results and providing value for all stakeholders. Dingle Peninsula Living Lab aims to achieve: i) a vibrant, strongly networked, transition-engaged community with a robust co-created vision of the future for the community; ii) sustainable strategies bringing that co-created vision into reality; iii) employment impact of 200+ jobs; iv) enabling conditions for 200+ new Connected (Home) Working incomes to be sustained on the Peninsula.

Areas of Work

- Agriculture & (Agri-)Food
- Circular Economy
- Culture & Creativity (creative sectors)
- Energy
- Environment/Climate Change
- Mobility
- Rural
- Social Innovation & Inclusion

Main Expertise

Co-creation Methods & Tools, Governance Models, Impact Assessments, Innovation Strategies, Living Lab Evaluation, Panel Management, Policy Making, Real-life Experimentation, Stakeholder Engagement, User & Living Lab Research

Adherent Member

NetwellCASALA

Dundalk Institute of Technology

Country: Ireland

www.netwellcasala.org

Type of Living Lab:

Research driven Living Lab

NetwellCASALA at Dundalk Institute of Technology is a research centre and Living Lab where digital health and wellbeing solutions are designed, developed, tested and tried with and for older people, and those who care for and about them, to empower and support better and longer living in the community. The Living Lab works collaboratively with multiple stakeholders in the public and private sectors, academia, and most importantly, with citizen end-users. It is committed to ensuring those most impacted by the work have an opportunity to contribute to person-centred research, through public and patient involvement (PPI) across different projects. Led by Suzanne Smith, the research-driven Living Lab co-produces innovative solutions with citizens, academia and the public, private and voluntary sectors focussed on Connected Age-Friendly Communities to support longer living in smarter places. Methods and tools are user and citizen-centred, applied in real-world contexts as well as in the Innovation and Performance Lab, and focused on co-production and knowledge valorisation of innovative solutions.

Areas of Work

- Health & Well Being

Main Expertise

Co-creation Methods & Tools, Governance Models, Impact Assessments, Living Lab Evaluation, Panel Management, Real-life Experimentation, Scaling-up, Stakeholder Engagement, User & Living Lab Research

Accepted to Grow

Homecare Innovation Technologies Lab (HIT-Lab)

Holon Institute of Technology

Country: Israel

<https://www.hit.ac.il>

Type of Living Lab:

Research driven Living Lab

HIT-Lab focuses on homecare technologies and: (i) supports stakeholders with solutions in real life setting starting from clinical partner's needs, to co-create and innovative solutions providing MVP for clinical trials and implementation healthcare setting; (ii) addresses the growth of the data challenge: as more Patient Generated- Data (PGD) are collected they develop tools and methodologies for collecting, managing and integrating PGD with EHR (Electronic-Health-Record) data; (iii) is connected in a satellite structure to labs with complementary expertise in data science, bio-medical engineering , AI-based applications, with multidisciplinary teams to address needs from idea to implementation; (iv) has courses in which students join multidisciplinary teams addressing homecare challenges. There is a training program of 6-months for physicians in their medical training (in collaboration with IMA -Israeli Medical Association) educating them to co-creation and multidisciplinary R&D.

Areas of Work

- AI and Emerging technologies
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Health & Well Being

Main Expertise

 Scaling-up						
 User & Living Lab Research						

ISRAEL

Adherent Member

City of the future Living Lab

San Raffaele Hospital

Country: Italy

www.hsr.it

Type of Living Lab:

Living Lab as a service
Living testbed
Research driven Living Lab

San Raffaele Scientific Institute’s City of the Future Living Lab in Milan has been created to observe an extended number of users interacting with a great number of services within a real city environment, as well as to engage them in a co-creation process that triggers and helps flourish tomorrow’s e-Services.

Areas of Work

- AI and Emerging technologies
- Health & Well Being
- Smart Cities & Regions

Main Expertise

 Real-life Experimentation						
 User & Living Lab Research						

ITALY

Adherent Member

Green Schools Living Lab

Provincia di Treviso

Country: Italy

www.trevisoscuole.it

Type of Living Lab:

Urban Living Lab

The Living Lab Green Schools of the Province of Treviso aims at changing users' behaviour to foster energy saving. To achieve this goal Green Schools uses the management of the school building as a model in which the user/student/teacher can actively participate thanks to the IT tools used for the managing activities, which are accessible through a web portal (www.trevisoscuole.it). Thus, Green Schools is an answer to the need of reducing the costs for managing buildings through a reduction of energy consumption and through a rational and conscious use of the common good. Green Schools furtherly provides an important educational added value as activities aiming at energy saving and sustainability are mainly addressed to, and

performed by, students and teachers. The main characteristics of Green Schools Living Lab are: i) users themselves, as well as technology, become a real "tool" for energy saving; ii) in the Green Schools Living Lab the roles of technology and users are complementary; iii) technology is the lever through which users are stimulated towards a virtuous behaviour and users efficiency can boost new technological investments on energy efficiency, creating a virtuous circle; iv) it has a spill over effect in the social context (socialization and respect for common resources), in informal learning (it stimulates learning through acting and action, even from a competitive point of view with the Green Schools Competition), in the technological field (users stimulate technologies such as smart metering) and in the economic field (virtuous behaviour reinforces the energy saving potentialities and therefore costs).

Areas of Work

- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Energy
- Environment/Climate Change

Main Expertise

Adherent Member

InnovAALab - Apulian Living Lab on "Healthy, Active & Assisted Living"

National Research Council of Italy

Country: Italy

Type of Living Lab:

Living Lab as a service
Living testbed
Research driven Living Lab

InnovAALab - the Apulian Living Lab on "Healthy, Active & Assisted Living" - was born as a part of the Strategic Plan and Vision of the activities of the Public-Private Partnership "INNOVAAL" (according the PPPP model), funded by the Ministry of Research in Italy in the field of Ambient Assisted Living (AAL), Independent Living, Ageing Well, Healthy Living, and related development of Products and Services. InnovAALab covers a large area at territorial level involving also the additional actors coming from the regional projects funded in the frame of "Health, Wellness and Socio-Cultural Dynamics" of the Apulian ICT Living Labs initiative.

Areas of Work

- Health & Well Being
- Smart Cities & Regions
- Social Innovation & Inclusion

Main Expertise

Adherent Member

KLIOLab - Knowledge-based Lifecycle InnOvation Laboratory

DHITECH (Distretto High Tech)

Country: Italy

Type of Living Lab:

Living testbed

KLIOLab represents a synergic partnership among public and private actors aimed at developing innovative ICT solutions for the aeronautic and mechanical industries through knowledge, practices and resource sharing and the creation of start-ups and spin-offs. KLIOLab has been created in 2014 by formalizing cooperative practices built through long-term cooperation among public and private partners of the DHITECH (Distretto High Tech), the Apulian district for high technology development, hosting organisation for the KLIOLab. Currently this partnership, composed of aeronautic industries, universities, high-competent spin-offs in the ICT industry, Public Administrations and students, is committed to the implementation and deployment of a methodological framework moving the product life cycle management from an enterprise-based view to a value network-based view. The main business line of KLIOLab embodies executing innovation projects, through public and private funds, and the involvement of different categories of users in the innovation process. The innovation pursued by KLIOLab is twofold: i) innovating Product Lifecycle Management system to push supply chain cooperation during the new complex product development process; ii) identifying and developing new industrial competencies for students, research staff, ICT start-ups, spin-offs and innovative enterprises, aeronautic SMEs as well as KHIRA project staff.

Areas of Work

- AI and Emerging technologies
- Culture & Creativity (creative sectors)
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Energy
- Environment/Climate Change
- Health & Well Being
- Industries & Manufacturing
- Mobility
- Smart Cities & Regions
- SME & Start-ups
- Social Innovation & Inclusion

Adherent Member

Lunigiana Amica

XR8 di Molinari Francesco & C. sas

Country: Italy

Type of Living Lab:

Rural Living Lab

Lunigiana Amica is a non-profit association born from the needs of local agricultural producers to promote their products through a short-range supply chain. Lunigiana Amica's goal is to connect and network the main actors of the agri-food system, setting up product marketing strategies within and outside the territory of Massa-Carrara province. The ultimate goal is to achieve positive effects for the members of the association and for the Lunigiana area. The association was born in 2007 and promoted by Coldiretti, CIA, Confcooperative, and the Municipality of Licciana Nardi.

Areas of Work

- Agriculture & (Agri-)Food
- Rural
- Other areas of work

Main Expertise

Business Model Innovation	Co-creation Methods & Tools	Governance Models	Impact Assessments	Implementation after Testing	Innovation Strategies	Living Lab Evaluation
Panel Management	Policy Making	Real-life Experimentation	Scaling-up	Service Design	Stakeholder Engagement	User & Living Lab Research

Effective Member

Mediterranean Innovation Rural Living Lab (MEDIL)

CIHEAM Bari

Country: Italy

www.iamb.it

Type of Living Lab:

Rural Living Lab

The Mediterranean Innovation Rural Living Lab aims to become a catalyst for innovation ecosystems promoting the sustainable development of rural and coastal areas in Apulia and the Mediterranean region. The lab's objectives include:

- Spreading the culture of Open-Innovation through the development of training courses, research, knowledge transfer, and international cooperation in the Mediterranean Area.
- Creating a multi-actor network that applies a systematic approach of co-creation, integrating research and innovation processes in communities and real-life environments.
- Generating innovation by supporting youth entrepreneurship and facilitating the co-design and acceleration of solutions for businesses, rural, and coastal communities.

Areas of Work

- Agriculture & (Agri-)Food
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- SME & Start-ups
- Social Innovation & Inclusion
- Water (Blue economy)

Main Expertise

Adherent Member

Puglia Smart Lab

DHITECH (Distretto High Tech)

Country: Italy

www.pugliasmartlab.dhitech.it/?lang=en

The Smart Community around Puglia Smart LL plays a fundamental role toward an holistic view aimed to understand the processes of change in the social, economic and organization contexts and to achieve an harmonious progression in the society, by listening to all the stakeholder in the territory. This approach already started, promotes the collaboration of citizens with all the stakeholders involved in service delivering. The “smart” use of new technologies, defined in Puglia@Service project to be used and tested within the Lab, enables service integration overcoming silos structure of the services, nowadays strictly divides between public and private. For this reason Puglia Smart LL aims to put in practise a radical change in delivery services for a territory, oriented to become a smart community. Puglia Smart LL is developed within the area of the “Internet-based Service Engineering”, devoted to the research of scientific analytical methodologies for the design, production and deployment of innovative services. Moreover it is positioned between Service Science and open innovation. The innovative characteristics of the LL are: i) a pervasive technological infrastructure, thought to act as the nervous system of the “smart territory”; ii) a qualified human capital, developed according to the profile of the “Innovator and Entrepreneur Engineer”, able to create economic and social value (Technological Entrepreneurship); iii) start-up specialized in the Service Engineering Area, able to facilitate the development of “technology-based” innovative services.

Adherent Member

Santa Chiara Lab
University of Siena

Country: Italy

www.santachiaralab.unisi.it

Type of Living Lab:

Living Lab as a service
Research driven Living Lab

Santa Chiara Lab is the innovation centre of the University of Siena. It is a place that catalyzes many cultural and social initiatives involving many actors (organizations, institutions, companies, Associations of the territory, students, and researchers) who see in the Santa Chiara Lab a place of knowledge exchange and permanent contamination. Santa Chiara Lab collaborates with citizens, universities, companies, cities and regions for joint value co-creation and co-design, rapid prototyping, experimenting and demonstrating concrete solutions to foster innovation, whilst supporting the transition from fundamental to applied research, in several domains such as sustainability, agrifood, public health, education, and digitalization.

Areas of Work

- Agriculture & (Agri-)Food
- Circular Economy
- Culture & Creativity (creative sectors)
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Environment/Climate Change
- Health & Well Being
- Industries & Manufacturing
- Rural
- Social Innovation & Inclusion
- Urban
- Zero Pollution & Decarbonization
- Other areas of work

Main Expertise

Adherent Member

Thriving Entrepreneurial and Creative Lab (TECLA)

EIS - Easy integrazione di sistemi s.r.l.

Country: Italy

www.easyint.it

Type of Living Lab:

Urban Living Lab

The Thriving Entrepreneurial and Creative Lab (TECLA) is an initiative that intends to exploit the potential of the Palermo city to become thriving and sustainable by leveraging and reinforcing the entrepreneurial and innovative capacity of local actors in the creative industry field. TECLA is a physical space that encourages participants to discuss ideas and projects, meet partners, and develop collaborative methodologies so that sustainable development goals can be supported by new technologies and advanced multimedia tools, as well as by knowledge in the social sciences, art and humanities. TECLA is managed by EIS, a private innovation management company and it is part of the creative hub CRE.ZI. PLUS, hosted in the cultural campus of the Palermo Municipality “Cantieri Culturali alla Zisa”. It capitalises the results of EU funded projects, and it is part of the Euro-Mediterranean network of U-SOLVE urban innovation hubs. TECLA has been building a diverse ecosystem of local and international enterprises active in different creative domains, which are engaged in joint projects and initiatives. TECLA’s activities also attract policy makers, academics, industry professionals, designers, manufacturers and other key actors in the urban community.

Areas of Work

- Circular Economy
- Culture & Creativity (creative sectors)
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Environment/Climate Change
- SME & Start-ups
- Social Innovation & Inclusion
- Urban

Main Expertise

Adherent Member

TIE-LL Technology Innovation Ecosystem

Apulian High Tech District

Country: Italy

www.dhitech.it

Type of Living Lab:

Research driven Living Lab

TIE Living Lab is hosted by DHITECH and stems from the research project VINCENTE (Virtual collective INtelligenCe ENvironment to develop sustainable Technology Entrepreneurship ecosystem), co-funded by the Italian Ministry of Education, University and Research. The TIE Living Lab's mission is to conceive and promote, openly and collaboratively, a personalizable ecosystem of actors and stakeholders, relationships and resources, actions and initiatives to support potential entrepreneurs and companies in cultivating innovative ideas and entrepreneurial projects as well as developing entrepreneurial competencies and attitudes. By favouring the arising of ideas and the exchange of knowledge and experiences, TIE Living Lab enables the open dialogue among scientists, researchers, companies, entrepreneurs and investors, citizen and associations, local authorities,

universities and public institutions to jointly conceive, design, and realize innovative solutions and entrepreneurial projects. These outcomes and flows contribute to the diffusion of an entrepreneurial culture and mindset in the entire region, to activate economic, social and cultural development processes which foster territorial growth and increase the attractiveness of the region itself.

Areas of Work

- Agriculture & (Agri-)Food
- AI and Emerging technologies
- Circular Economy
- Culture & Creativity (creative sectors)
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Energy
- Environment/Climate Change
- Health & Well Being
- Industries & Manufacturing
- Mobility
- Research
- Smart Cities & Regions
- SME & Start-ups
- Social Innovation & Inclusion

Main Expertise

Business Model Innovation	Innovation Strategies	Stakeholder Engagement	User & Living Lab Research

Adherent Member

Torino City Lab
City of Turin

Country: Italy

www.torinocitylab.it

Type of Living Lab:

Urban Living Lab

Torino City lab works as a real-life laboratory open to all companies interested in testing “innovative solutions of public interest in Turin”. Specific challenges or priority areas can be identified periodically and allow starting “thematic laboratories”. Torino City Lab (TCL) is an initiative-platform aimed at creating simplified conditions for companies interested in conducting testing in real conditions of innovative solutions for urban living. The initiative was launched in 2018 by the City of Turin and today has about 90 international and national partners. Since 2021, the “House of Emerging Technologies of Turin - CTE NEXT” has been inaugurated, which grafts on Torino City Lab, expanding its purposes towards the acceleration of start-ups and technology transfer in the field of emerging technologies enabled by 5G in verticals of interest to Turin, such as: land and air mobility, Industry 4.0 and Smart City.

Areas of Work

- Circular Economy
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Energy
- Environment/Climate Change
- Mobility
- Smart Cities & Regions
- SME & Start-ups
- Social Innovation & Inclusion

Main Expertise

Business Model Innovation	Co-creation Methods & Tools	Governance Models	Impact Assessments	Implementation after Testing	Innovation Strategies	Living Lab Evaluation
Panel Management	Policy Making	Real-life Experimentation	Scaling-up	Service Design	Stakeholder Engagement	User & Living Lab Research

Adherent Member

Innovative Learning & Teacher Education Living Lab (IL.TE.LL)

University of Mauritius

Country: Mauritius

www.uom.ac.mu

Type of Living Lab:

Living testbed

Innovative Learning & Teacher Education Living Lab (IL.TE.LL) is based on a multiple-impact social partnership (MISP) model and is essentially an integration of the Research and Development model that has governed LL's applied research activities in education technology, and a community engagement model when members involved in the Living Lab established a non-governmental organisation through an entity called Helping Our People. It is based on Whitehead's education research philosophy for social change through action research and the Living lab paradigm for Teaching and Learning. The MISP model fits in the 4P innovation framework where the Public sector is represented by the University, the Private Sector is represented by Microsoft Indian Ocean and French Pacific, with the People being academics, educators, and Youth volunteers (students). The beneficiaries and the partnerships among these

actors are mediated through a collective social movement called Helping Our People. The Research and Development Model (Cycle 1) is based on a practitioner-oriented concept where research and development essentially become the drivers for practice-oriented enquiries to improve teaching and learning systems. It aims at field experimentation to test new practices, which are then formalized into teaching methods that can be cascaded down to educators for classroom application. The educators at the receiving end also become engaged in an action-reflection cycle where the feedback is fed into the system for continuous improvement and refinement of teaching techniques and the application of ICT tools in day-to-day practice.

Areas of Work

- AI and Emerging technologies
- Education and/or Vocational Training

Main Expertise

Business Model Innovation	Implementation after Testing	Innovation Strategies	Policy Making	Real-life Experimentation	Scaling-up	Stakeholder Engagement

MAURITIUS

Adherent Member

ADP Zid Living Lab

Community Impact Accelerator - Zid

Country: Montenegro

www.zid.org.me

Type of Living Lab:

Living Lab as a service
Research driven Living Lab

Community Impact Accelerator – Zid was established ADP-Zid Living Lab three years ago. But, throughout our 9-year experience in implementation of co-creative methodologies, we have adopted and practiced Living Lab principles to foster innovation in the Montenegrin community and to tackle societal challenges. As an accelerator, ADP-Zid supports and creates community transformation solutions, which are based on connecting actors, innovative methodologies, research and technology transfer. The Accelerator organizes its work through three sectors: - Technology Transfer and Innovation Development Centre, which comprises of several supporting units – Living lab, Research Centre and I2 Maker Space; - Solidary Economy and Entrepreneurship Development sector, within which the Community Support Business Cluster functions; and - Resource Centre for Active Participation.

Areas of Work

- Circular Economy
- Energy
- Mobility
- Policies
- Social Innovation & Inclusion

Main Expertise

Co-creation Methods & Tools	Governance Models	Panel Management	Policy Making	Service Design	Stakeholder Engagement	User & Living Lab Research

Adherent Member

Blauwe Hotspot Dordrecht (Blue Hub)

Stichting Yuverta

Country: Netherlands

www.blauwehotspotdordrecht.nl

Type of Living Lab:

Living testbed
 Research driven Living Lab
 Urban Living Lab
 Rural Living Lab

Involving The Blue Hotspot in the decision-making and strategy development process, Yuverta ensures that it stays ahead of the curve and remains relevant in a rapidly changing world, playing a crucial role in fostering collaboration and knowledge sharing among diverse stakeholders. People with diverse backgrounds contribute with unique perspectives and expertise to tackle complex challenges facing education and job market. Hotspots are the engine of Yuverta in its mission to transform education and research. With a network of linked hubs across different regions, Yuverta ensures that its strategies are tailored to meet specific needs and demands of each community. Looking to 2030, hotspots will clearly continue to play a central role in driving innovation, promoting sustainable practices, fostering an entrepreneurial spirit in Yuverta. Harnessing collective power of hotspots, Yuverta is well-positioned to lead the way to shape the future of education and of a more sustainable society.

Areas of Work

- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Environment/Climate Change
- Research
- Rural
- Soil
- Water (Blue economy)

Main Expertise

 Real-life Experimentation						
 User & Living Lab Research						

Adherent Member

Care Innovation Center West-Brabant

Care Innovation Center

Country: Netherlands

www.cic-westbrabant.nl

Type of Living Lab:

Living testbed
Living Lab as a service
Rural Living Lab

The Care Innovation Centre West Brabant is a foundation and network organization that contributes to the development and implementation of innovations by stimulating, connecting, and supporting healthcare- and welfare organizations, educational institutions, and businesses that contribute to innovation in healthcare. The Centre initiates projects that contribute to innovations, inspired by the concept of Positive Health, through the organisation of knowledge and inspiration sessions, arranging workshop series, initiating and supporting innovation projects, and launching training programs. By doing so, the Care Innovation Centre West Brabant contributes to prevention, sustainable care, increasing job satisfaction, and reducing workload. The Centre established sustainable collaborations with a core group of partners who endorse its vision and are committed to the same goals. We make innovation accessible by sharing knowledge, contacts, successes, and failures.

Areas of Work

- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Health & Well Being
- SME & Start-ups
- Social Innovation & Inclusion

Main Expertise

Innovation Partner

Delft University of Technology

Delft University of Technology (faculty of Technology, Policy and Management)

Country: Netherlands

<https://www.tudelft.nl/en/>

As a leading academic institution in the field of engineering, technology and innovation in the Netherlands, Delft University of Technology and its faculty members are engaged in cutting-edge research in innovation studies, sustainable development, governance, and decision-making, with a strong focus on user-centric and interdisciplinary collaborations. We house various labs and a number of research groups focused on fostering innovation. These include: the Design for Values Institute, which explores how technology can be designed and governed to align with human values; the Samelab, which develops serious games; and the Transdisciplinary Lab for Learning and Research, which tests, explores and reflects upon innovative co-creative processes to address scientific and societal challenges in research and education. These labs provide platforms for collaborative research, experimentation, and knowledge exchange, forming a research ecosystem oriented to technological innovation and learning.

Areas of Work

- Circular Economy
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Energy
- Environment/Climate Change
- Health & Well Being
- Mobility
- Smart Cities & Regions
- Social Innovation & Inclusion
- Soil
- Water (Blue economy)

Effective Member

Eindhoven Living Lab

City of Eindhoven

Country: Netherlands

www.eindhoven.nl

Type of Living Lab:

Living testbed
Living Lab as a service
Urban Living Lab
Research driven Living Lab

Situated in the centre of the Brainport Eindhoven region, the city of Eindhoven has a strong commitment towards its citizens to enhance the quality of life, by mobilising the creative power of triple helix parties and citizens/end users all together. It is also opening the city itself as a real-life testing ground for products and services with an added value that meet the needs, ambitions and concerns of the end users. Bringing together partners on the one hand and creating/contributing to structures in which partners can meet on the other hand are the two main points that are to characterise Eindhoven Living Lab, which is the umbrella approach to incorporate these Living Labs and future ones into one, more integrated and integral approach. Eindhoven Living Lab is about: i) Living Labs in which the City of Eindhoven is taking an active lead role; ii) Living Labs in which the City of Eindhoven is taking a minor role as a partner, or which are merely facilitated by the City by providing the necessary infrastructure and the access to it; in this case the Living Lab can extend beyond the territory of the city.

Areas of Work

- AI and Emerging technologies
- Circular Economy
- Culture & Creativity (creative sectors)
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Energy
- Environment/Climate Change
- Health & Well Being
- Industries & Manufacturing
- Mobility
- Regulatory Learning
- Smart Cities & Regions
- SME & Start-ups
- Social Innovation & Inclusion
- Urban
- Zero Pollution & Decarbonization
- Other areas of work

Main Expertise

Innovation Partner

South-Holland Impact Alliance

The Hague University of Applied Sciences

Country: Netherlands

The Dutch society is facing a multitude of challenges, impending labour market shortages, rising healthcare costs, increasing health disparities, new security threats, and adaptation to climate change, requiring innovative approaches and contextual tackling. The four major Universities of Applied Sciences in South Holland, namely – The Hague University of Applied Sciences (THUAS), InHolland University of Applied Sciences (InHolland), Rotterdam University of Applied Sciences (RUAS), Leiden University of Applied Sciences (LUAS) established the South-Holland Impact Alliance (SHIA). SHIA has experience and expertise, thanks to the strong ties with stakeholders in the local neighbourhoods, the cities and the province itself. Netherlands recognizes the SHIA as a powerful, recognizable knowledge and innovation network. SHIA is recognizable in the areas of Health, Care, and Well-being, Sustainability, and AI and has actively contributed at reducing health disparities in the region.

Areas of Work

- AI and Emerging technologies
- Circular Economy
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Energy
- Environment/Climate Change
- Health & Well Being
- Rural
- Smart Cities & Regions
- SME & Start-ups
- Water (Blue economy)
- Zero Pollution & Decarbonization

Adherent Member

Urban Leisure & Tourism Lab

Inholland University of Applied Sciences

Country: Netherlands

<https://www.inholland.nl>

Type of Living Lab:

Urban Living Lab

The Urban Leisure & Tourism Lab was founded by the Inholland University of Applied Sciences and it is based in Amsterdam and Rotterdam. It is at the forefront of addressing societal challenges through urban tourism, leading the way in shaping sustainable solutions for the future of the Leisure and Tourism industry.

The LL operates as a dynamic platform for (trans)disciplinary applied education and research, promoting collaboration across diverse domains of expertise and knowledge areas. This approach ensures projects are firmly grounded in the real world - yielding impactful research, innovative tools, thought leadership, and publications. Rooted in the community, the LL adopt a quintuple helix perspective - taking biodiversity into account, maintaining a longitudinal focus, and being committed to leaving a legacy through their interventions.

Areas of Work

- Culture & Creativity (creative sectors)
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Health & Well Being
- Research
- Smart Cities & Regions
- Social Innovation & Inclusion
- Urban

Main Expertise

Adherent Member

Urban Management - Fieldlabs

The Amsterdam University of Applied Sciences

Country: Netherlands

www.hva.nl/urban-management/fieldlabs/fieldlabs-urban-management.html

The Urban Management Fieldlabs are hosted by the Amsterdam University of Applied Sciences in collaboration with Amsterdam Municipality.

Urban Management Fieldlabs develop innovative approaches to metropolitan problems. Urban Management Fieldlabs were initiated in collaboration with stakeholders in three areas of the city: Nieuw-est, Zuidoost, and Oost. The Fieldlabs focus on developing area-based solutions to tangible urban challenges through co-creation. Together with local stakeholders, a shared long-term research and innovation agenda is formulated at the start of each Fieldlab. To ensure the focus on challenges that are specific to the areas in which the Fieldlabs are based, the local strategic development plan of the city district forms the starting point in developing this agenda. The UM Fieldlabs function as continuous learning environments focusing on the development of knowledge, but also on the improvement of practice through the direct application of acquired knowledge in tangible interventions. Because of the dynamic, complex and multi-faceted character of urban issues, addressing them will never be possible by only focusing on one aspect. The UM Fieldlabs are local innovation milieus aiming to contribute to the social innovation needed to address multi-scalar, multi-actor and multi-disciplinary urban challenges. A multi-disciplinary research team that is constituted based on the nature of the issue at hand is involved to ensure well informed decisions are made.

Adherent Member

WaterCampus Leeuwarden

Municipality of Leeuwarden

Country: Netherlands

www.leeuwarden.nl

Type of Living Lab:

Living Lab as a service
Research driven Living Lab

At the WaterCampus Leeuwarden, innovations in the field of water technology are developed, tested, upscaled and introduced in the global market. The WaterCampus is a host to a variety of testing locations where new applications can be tested in close cooperation with end users. The WaterCampus does not focus on any particular development stage. Innovative ideas on TRLs 1-9 are guided to the market. End-users (in the field of water technology often industries and utilities) are involved in every step of the innovation process through membership of, or partnership with, one of the managing partners: from determining the research program to testing the innovations in various Living Labs. The WaterCampus employs a highly skilled staff and is equipped with high quality research and innovation facilities and, including a set of real-life demo sites to test innovations in. Over the years, the WaterCampus has become a mature Living Lab which involves roughly 300 businesses and knowledge institutions, is active in multiple European programs and has become a household name in the field of water technology.

Areas of Work

- Agriculture & (Agri-)Food
- Circular Economy
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Energy
- Environment/Climate Change
- Health & Well Being
- Rural
- Smart Cities & Regions
- SME & Start-ups
- Water (Blue economy)
- Zero Pollution & Decarbonization

Main Expertise

Business Model Innovation	Co-creation Methods & Tools	Impact Assessments	Implementation after Testing	Innovation Strategies	Living Lab Evaluation	Panel Management
Real-life Experimentation	Scaling-up	Service Design	Stakeholder Engagement	User & Living Lab Research		

NORWAY

Adherent Member

Wireless Trondheim Living Lab

NTNU - Norwegian University of Science and Technology

Country: Norway

www.ntnu.edu

Type of Living Lab:

Urban Living Lab

The Wireless Trondheim Living Lab was originally established as a local arena in Trondheim, Norway, for open and user driven innovation related to mobile services and technology. In the last years, it has turned into a more general facility supporting stakeholder engagement for smart and sustainable cities. By being a member of ENoLL, it aims to extend and improve the development of services through increased influx of ideas and resources by engaging with users, in particular, students and school children, and also participants from other Living Labs.

Areas of Work

- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Mobility
- Urban

Main Expertise

 Service Design						
 User & Living Lab Research						

POLAND

Effective Member

Krakow Living Lab
Krakow Technology Park

Country: Poland

www.kpt.krakow.pl/en

Type of Living Lab:

Living Lab as a service

The Kraków Living Lab is a platform for testing products and services in the conditions in which they are used in life. Tests are conducted in the final/target context of use and operations not only verify the product concept but also point to the potential challenges and unforeseen aspects of use. The process of testing follows a structured iterative plan from concept via prototype to the implementation proper.

Areas of Work

- AI and Emerging technologies
- Circular Economy
- Culture & Creativity (creative sectors)
- Environment/Climate Change
- Industries & Manufacturing
- Mobility
- Smart Cities & Regions
- SME & Start-ups
- Social Innovation & Inclusion
- Zero Pollution & Decarbonization

Main Expertise

Effective Member

PSNC Future Labs
PSNC

Country: Poland

www.futurelabs.psnc.pl

Type of Living Lab:

Research driven Living Lab

PSNC Future Labs Real people - actual problems - digital innovations. PSNC FutureLabs is a Living Laboratory, involving the citizens of Poznań and PSNC regional partners in the design of digital innovations and business models. The Living Lab animates local communities of innovators, entrepreneurs and social activists. With 2000+ sqm of advanced IT labs on six floors, it is a space where cutting-edge technologies support the mission of Wielkopolska region smart specializations. PSNC initiates innovative city projects and secures their financing. It also supports the UN Sustainable Development Goals locally and addresses grand challenges of the Horizon Europe thematic clusters. With support from R&D and business partners, it developed HPC4Poland Digital Innovation Hub.

Areas of Work

- AI and Emerging technologies
- Culture & Creativity (creative sectors)
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Environment/Climate Change
- Health & Well Being
- Industries & Manufacturing
- Media
- Smart Cities & Regions
- SME & Start-ups
- Social Innovation & Inclusion

Main Expertise

Adherent Member

GreenLab@Lisbon - Tapada da Ajuda Campus the Lisbon Green Lab

Instituto Superior de Agronomia/ School of Agriculture (Universidade de Lisboa)

Country: Portugal

<https://www.isa.ulisboa.pt>

Type of Living Lab:

Living Lab as a service
Research driven Living Lab

The Instituto Superior de Agronomia (ISA) is a leading academic institution for efficient and sustainable agriculture and forestry, food innovation, bio-circularity of product chains, management of natural resources and territories. ISA is part of the University of Lisbon, the largest and highest-ranked university in Portugal, located in the heart of Lisbon, in a campus spanning an impressive 100 ha. GreenLab@Lisbon is an integral part of ISA, it promotes collaborative projects with researchers, students, companies, the public sector, and the society. It works as an innovation hub driving progress in smart and sustainable practices and fostering proactive learning attitudes, with a vision that prioritizes open education, research, and knowledge dissemination. GreenLab also accommodates spin-off companies and private enterprises aligned with ISA's mission, becoming a valuable asset for the global innovation community, enabling user-driven innovation and progress to a brighter future.

Areas of Work

- Agriculture & (Agri-)Food
- Circular Economy
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Environment/Climate Change
- Research
- SME & Start-ups
- Soil

Main Expertise

 Real-life Experimentation						
 User & Living Lab Research						

PORTUGAL

Adherent Member

Montado Living Lab

Universidade de Évora

Country: Portugal

Type of Living Lab:

Rural Living Lab
Research driven Living Lab

The LL Montado main focus is the development, testing, and promotion of sustainable practices to enhance the multifunctionality of the Montado system with a focus on soil health, restoration of the structure, namely the tree cover, and promoting biodiversity assuring a socio-economic balance in this crucial agro-silvo-pastoral system.

The LL aims at building capacities and tailored solutions using co-construction approaches, involving input from multiple stakeholders with relevance for the Montado system, namely Academia, Associations, Public Administration and Companies with activities linked with the Montado. This collaborative effort facilitates knowledge sharing, learning, innovation, and technological development to optimise Montado solutions.

Areas of Work

- Agriculture & (Agri-)Food
- Circular Economy
- Environment/Climate Change
- Policies
- Research
- Rural
- Soil
- Zero Pollution & Decarbonization

Main Expertise

Business Model Innovation, Co-creation Methods & Tools, Governance Models, Impact Assessments, Implementation after Testing, Innovation Strategies, Living Lab Evaluation, Policy Making, Real-life Experimentation, Scaling-up, Stakeholder Engagement, User & Living Lab Research

Adherent Member

Smart Rural Living Lab

Municipality of Penela

Country: Portugal

<https://www.cm-penela.pt/>

Type of Living Lab:

Rural Living Lab

The Smart Rural Living Lab (SRL) aims to generate new methodologies and technologies to approach rural territories weaknesses and strengths, and by these becoming a reference in sustainable rural development, exporting knowledge to other territories, and working with users to foster this specific region. The problems faced by this type of territory, as the Penela Municipality, are primarily focused on improving the local economic base and develop the natural resources, promoting citizenship and entrepreneurship, increasing welfare and social development, tourism promotion and territory identity preservation.

Areas of Work

- Agriculture & (Agri-)Food
- Circular Economy
- Environment/Climate Change
- Rural
- SME & Start-ups

Main Expertise

Co-creation Methods & Tools, Governance Models, Implementation after Testing, Innovation Strategies, Panel Management, Policy Making, Real-life Experimentation, Scaling-up, Service Design, Stakeholder Engagement, User & Living Lab Research

Adherent Member

Daegu Creative Living Lab

Daegu Technopark (Digital Transformation Agency)

Country: Republic of Korea

<https://dgtp.or.kr/eng/information.html>

Type of Living Lab:

Living testbed
Living Lab as a service
Urban Living Lab

The Daegu Technopark operates a city innovation platform through Living Lab. It trains citizens to create innovation seeds to participate in Living Labs and trains diverse citizens to become citizen scientists. The organisation helps solve urban problems by operating various Living Labs such as Social Living Lab, Alley Living Lab, and Smart City Living Lab, centring on trained citizen scientists. It also promotes the cultures that change the city through the Living Lab, and ultimately serve as a window for a sustainable city.

Areas of Work

- AI and Emerging technologies
- Industries & Manufacturing
- Smart Cities & Regions
- Social Innovation & Inclusion

Main Expertise

 Panel Management						
 User & Living Lab Research						

REPUBLIC OF KOREA

Adherent Member

Smart Safety Living Lab

Korea Institute of Industrial Technology (KITECH)

Country: Republic of Korea

www.sssl.knicc.re.kr

Type of Living Lab:

Research Drive Living Lab

Smart Safety Living Lab is an innovative platform that encourages the participation of stakeholders and users to reflect user experiences in the development process of new products and services for SMEs. To support user-participatory innovation activities, the Korea National Industrial Convergence Centre at the Korea Institute of Industrial Technology has established spaces that simulate real product and service usage environments and has built equipment to collect and analyse user and environmental information. In collaboration with specialized institutions, the centre supports activities necessary at each stage of the development, including: business model planning, developing concepts considering market demand and creating business models for successful commercialization; user experience validation, evaluating and verifying usability, safety, and user experience value; certification services, providing consulting for test certifications, test evaluations, and developing standards.

Areas of Work

- Health & Well Being
- Media
- SME & Start-ups

Main Expertise

Business Model Innovation	Co-creation Methods & Tools	Governance Models	Living Lab Evaluation	Panel Management	Policy Making	Real-life Experimentation
Scaling-up	Service Design	Stakeholder Engagement	User & Living Lab Research			

ROMANIA

Accepted to Grow

Agrodatasmart

Agricultural Research and Development Station of Braila

Country: Romania

<https://www.scdabraila.ro>

Type of Living Lab:

Research driven Living Lab
Rural Living Lab

AGRODATASMART LL is coordinated by ARDS Braila (Agricultural Research-Development Station) whose motto is "Research for well-being", together with the AGROSMART Cluster "Together we are better and stronger" an association comprising 15 members (farmers, universities, companies, local authorities).

AGRODATASMART is a Living Lab that aims to develop precision agriculture in Romania. Therefore, the digitization of agriculture is promoted, through the use of sensors, satellite images, weather stations and drones, for the supervision of agricultural and horticultural crops and the timely adoption of phytosanitary treatment measures. The main objective is to reduce as much as possible the use of pesticides and to protect the environment.

Areas of Work

- Agriculture & (Agri-)Food
- AI and Emerging technologies
- Circular Economy
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Environment/Climate Change
- Research
- Soil

Main Expertise

Business Model Innovation, Co-creation Methods & Tools, Governance Models, Impact Assessments, Implementation after Testing, Innovation Strategies, Real-life Experimentation, Scaling-up, Service Design, Stakeholder Engagement, User & Living Lab Research

Accepted to Grow

NEXUS BEIA 2050 Living Lab

Beia Consult International SRL

Country: Romania

<https://beiaro.eu>

Type of Living Lab:

Living testbed
Urban Living Lab

The Nexus BEIA 2050 Living Lab aims to support the implementation of clean technologies for sustainable and resilient growth of agri-food sector based on a more efficient use of energy (renewable/solar/hydrogen) and water management in the Balkan thanks to the contribution of ICT technologies like: AI, Blockchain, cloud, big data, quantum), Telemetry (IIoT, IoMT), data analytics, processing, front/back-end, interfaces.

With an international partnership spanning over, NEXUS LL supports strengthening the technology transfer, cooperation between the 4 major actors of Quadruple Helix model, increasing commercialization opportunities and innovation-driven growth in the region. NEXUS LL offers comprehensive indoor and outdoor facilities as test-bed for food, water and energy solutions, offering a wide range of capabilities.

Areas of Work

- Agriculture & (Agri-)Food
- Energy
- Water (Blue economy)

Main Expertise

Business Model Innovation, Co-creation Methods & Tools, Governance Models, Impact Assessments, Implementation after Testing, Innovation Strategies, Living Lab Evaluation, Panel Management, Policy Making, Real-life Experimentation, Scaling-up, Service Design, Stakeholder Engagement, User & Living Lab Research

Accepted to Grow

Ovidius Aqua Line Living Lab

Ovidius Aqua Line S.R.L.

Country: Romania

<https://ovidiusaqualine.ro>

Ovidius Aqua Line Living Lab, located on the Danube River in Borcea, Calarasi County, Romania, is dedicated to advancing sustainable aquaculture, focusing on sturgeon. The facility promotes ecological farming and environmental protection, producing high-quality, environmentally friendly products. It features a state-of-the-art indoor fish farm and processing facility, yielding 25 tons annually of sturgeon, trout, and caviar. The lab utilizes high-end IoT equipment for real-time monitoring and control, a backup power supply, modular design fiberglass ponds, and an in-house production unit of concentrated oxygen. Its living lab methodology emphasizes user-centric innovation through co-creation, demonstration, testing, and evaluation of cutting-edge aquaculture solutions.

Areas of Work

- Agriculture & (Agri-)Food
- Environment/Climate Change
- Health & Well Being
- Industries & Manufacturing
- Rural
- SME & Start-ups

TRANSILVANIA IT
CLUSTER

Adherent Member

Transilvania Living Lab

Asociatia Transilvania IT

Country: Romania

www.transilvaniait.ro

Type of Living Lab:

Living testbed
Urban Living Lab
Living Lab as a service
Research driven Living Lab

Transilvania Living Lab aims to identify cross-sectorial projects with all stakeholders from the regional innovative ecosystem. Transilvania Living Lab strives to put communities and their needs at the heart of innovation, developing and experimenting with projects and services that involve smart approaches. The goal of Transilvania Living Lab is to empower the users of its services (citizens of the region, private companies, clusters, universities, research institutes, public administration) and integrate them into the innovation process, motivating them to participate, putting the right tools in place to enable a bottom-up dialogue, and translating ideas into sustainable commercial products or services. The host organization of Transilvania Living Lab works with a wide range of stakeholders, within a public-private-people partnership, trying to provide solutions and cooperation in areas such as ICT, eHealth, eGovernment, education, space, climate change, Earth Observation, social innovation, smart cities and regions.

Areas of Work

- Agriculture & (Agri-)Food
- AI and Emerging technologies
- Circular Economy
- Culture & Creativity (creative sectors)
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Energy
- Environment/Climate Change
- Health & Well Being
- Industries & Manufacturing
- Policies
- Research
- Smart Cities & Regions
- SME & Start-ups
- Urban
- Zero Pollution & Decarbonization

Main Expertise

 Living Lab Evaluation						
 User & Living Lab Research						

Effective Member

UVT Digital & Green Living Lab
West University of Timisoara

Country: Romania

www.livinglab.uvt.ro

Type of Living Lab:

Urban Living Lab
Living Lab as a service
Research driven Living Lab

Being a comprehensive University, that encompasses both STEAM domains, as well as Social Sciences & Humanities, Culture & Creativity and other associated topics, the West University of Timisoara is the first Romanian University to host a Living Lab. Focusing on meaningful transformation projects that contribute to enhanced community wellbeing, the UVT Digital & Green Living Lab makes use of digital and green tools for transformation projects, benefitting from the education and research human capital & infrastructure. Contributing to community wellbeing is the ultimate goal of the UVT Digital & Green Living Lab. Along with the dedicated digital (AI, ML, IoT, HPC, Cloud Computing) and green (Circular economy, Renewable energies, Urban gardens and green buildings, Biodiversity and Sustainable Development) tools, health and wellbeing is being addressed by the UVT LL with capabilities

related to green jobs & ergonomics, psychotherapy and spiritual wellbeing, physiotherapy and telerehabilitation, sports and healthy lifestyle, nutrition and dietetics, including functional foods and bioactive compounds.

Areas of Work

- AI and Emerging technologies
- Circular Economy
- Culture & Creativity (creative sectors)
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Energy
- Environment/Climate Change
- Gender
- Health & Well Being
- Media
- Mobility
- Policies
- Regulatory Learning
- Research
- Rural
- Smart Cities & Regions
- SME & Start-ups
- Social Innovation & Inclusion
- Soil
- Urban
- Water (Blue economy)
- Zero Pollution & Decarbonization

Main Expertise

 Scaling-up						
 Stakeholder Engagement						

RUSSIA

Adherent Member

Living Lab Tomsk Network (LLTNET)

Tomsk State University of Architecture and Building

Country: Rusia

www.livinglabtomsk.org

Type of Living Lab:

Urban Living Lab

Living Lab Tomsk Network is: i) the territory of experiments in real urban environment for testing products, technologies, and new approaches in the field of sustainable development of cities; ii) wonderful example of university campuses being used as Living Labs for distributing the culture of experimentation in the city, introduction of novel solutions and encouragement of entrepreneurship in young generations; iii) the initiative by a team of professionals of the United Tomsk University (that includes 6 universities of Tomsk), innovative companies and local communities, regional and municipal administration, in collaboration with foreign partners.

Living Lab Tomsk Network has 7 locations in its network, each with its focus of experiments: i) public space design; ii) smart

greening and water management; iii) smart management - healthy lifestyle; iv) multicultural environments; v) street art and creativity; vi) mobility; vii) dialog of generations. Experiments are initiated by students, young practitioners and professionals, all together organized in temporary design studios and workshops.

Areas of Work

- Culture & Creativity (creative sectors)
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Environment/Climate Change
- Health & Well Being
- Smart Cities & Regions
- Social Innovation & Inclusion
- Urban

Main Expertise

 Living Lab Evaluation						
 User & Living Lab Research						

Adherent Member

BELgrade Urban Living LAB
BELgrade Urban Living LAB

Country: Serbia

www.bellab.rs

BELgrade urban living LAB (BELLAB) is a collaborative environment where citizens, the public sector, planning experts, and private companies work together to co-create solutions in response to complex urban and climate-related challenges, e.g. climate change adaptation, disaster risk reduction and climate resilience, reduction of air and soil pollution, urban biodiversity protection, healthy city promotion, sustainable urban mobility planning. BELLAB was established in 2020, as a result of inter-institutional collaboration on two Horizon 2020 projects related to climate change mapping and adaptation strategies: CLEVER Cities and TeRRIFICA, as the first Urban Living Lab in Serbia and the Western Balkans. As such, it has a high potential to pave the road for ULL approach dissemination within the region. BELLAB is more than just a testbed platform since it provides experimentation in a real-life setting, located in the city of Belgrade. Amidst rising urbanization and political challenges, intensified by the global ecological and economic crisis, the Living Lab approach provides a new and creative solution for the implementation of public policies and urban design projects. The multifaceted goal of BELLAB is to overcome silos thinking caused by disciplinary boundaries, to envisage and engage various groups of stakeholders, empower citizens, to bridge top-down and bottom-up initiatives, and provide a shared vision of better quality of life in Belgrade.

Effective Member

PA4ALL - Precision Agriculture for All
BioSense Institute

Country: Serbia

www.biosens.rs

Type of Living Lab:

Rural Living Lab

PA4ALL – Precision Agriculture Living Lab is the first living laboratory in Serbia and one of the first in Europe to focus on precision agriculture. PA4ALL takes full advantage of inter-sectoral cross-fertilization of ideas and offers possibilities to test ideas and prototypes in the real-world setting. PA4ALL based its activities on educating its community on precision agriculture, motivating end-users to test and validate the IT innovations and ensuring their adoption among various stakeholders. PA4ALL activities are bridging the gap between the leisurely changing public sector and modern technologies which are modifying the way agriculture is perceived today. By reinforcing co-creation and multistakeholder participation, PA4ALL is not only gradually widening its network but also encouraging and supporting new

Living Labs which emerged in the region in the meantime. In addition to the abovementioned, throughout the Living Lab approach, PA4ALL plans to create a future network of actors who are expected to closely cooperate in the field of agroecology, which is a new concept thriving to become a pivotal change in the way agriculture production impacts then environment. PA4ALL also encourages the academia to engage more with the users of research, industry, government, and other relevant actors in order to implement precision agriculture in real-life decisionmaking processes.

Areas of Work

- Agriculture & (Agri-)Food
- Circular Economy
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Environment/Climate Change

Main Expertise

 Policy Making						
 User & Living Lab Research						

Adherent Member

PCNA LIVING LAB
Pannonian Climate Neutral Agriculture

**Pannonia
Climate Neutral
Agriculture Living
Lab**

University of Novi Sad,
Faculty of Agriculture

Country: Serbia

<https://agrocampus.rs/>

Type of Living Lab:

Rural Living Lab
Research driven Living
Lab

The Pannonian Climate Neutral Agriculture Living lab - PCNA LL epitomizes the definition of being a regional orchestrator of well-coordinated open innovation processes for co-created innovations in real-world settings for climate neutral solutions in agriculture. The PCNA LL's members are the leading actors of the agricultural sector in Vojvodina region on of the part of the Pannonian region. The UNSFA is the largest agricultural faculty in the Western Balkans, while AgroCampus is the largest demo farm in the country. ABE is a regional leading cluster organization in the field of regenerative agriculture with wide dissemination reach. IRI is an economic think tank that covers social science aspects of PCNA LL related to multi-actor engagement, co-creation and open innovation, sustainable business models, impact assessments, and socio-economic analyses. The PCNA LL is a beacon of open innovation allowing companies and researchers to test innovations in a real-life environment.

Areas of Work

- Agriculture & (Agri-)Food
- Circular Economy
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Zero Pollution & Decarbonisation

Main Expertise

 Real-life Experimentation						
 User & Living Lab Research						

SLOVENIA

Adherent Member

E-zavod Living Lab

E-zavod

Country: Slovenia

www.ezavod.si

Type of Living Lab:

Rural Living Lab
Living Lab as a service

E-zavod living lab focuses on transfer and mainstreaming of open innovation practices to Slovenia.

Work is focused on different areas and is mainly project driven. E-zavod Living Lab focuses on the following thematic sectors: Circular economy, Energy Efficiency and renewable energy, Textile sector, Smart cities, Nature based solutions.

Areas of Work

- Agriculture & (Agri-)Food
- Circular Economy
- Culture & Creativity (creative sectors)
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Energy
- Environment/Climate Change
- Rural
- Smart Cities & Regions
- SME & Start-ups
- Social Innovation & Inclusion

Main Expertise

Adherent Member

GREEN POINT Living Lab

ITC - Innovation technology Cluster Murska Sobota

Country: Slovenia

<https://itc-cluster.com/green-point/>

Type of Living Lab:

Rural Living Lab
Living testbed
Research driven Living Lab

Green Point Living is a fully operational Living Lab, the biggest and most advanced regional short food supply chain, founded by farmers, involving more than one hundred local farmers, food producers and cooperatives, covering the process of production in green house and open-air fields, with logistics from own distribution centre.

Green Point operates as a Living Lab based on a Multi-Actor Approach, involving input industry and technology providers, primary producers, food businesses, consumers, citizens, local authorities and other actors, promoting the co-creation of innovative systemic solutions to support food systems sustainability goals.

Areas of Work

- Circular Economy
- Environment/Climate Change
- Rural
- Soil

Main Expertise

Adherent Member

Alimentta

Alimentta, Think Tank for the Food Transition

Country: Spain

<https://alimentta.com>

Type of Living Lab:

Research driven Living Lab

Alimentta was born in 2019 as a Think Tank to accelerate the transition towards sustainable food systems in Spain. Its action is organised around three main streams: 1) the co-production of high-quality scientific knowledge on topics such as the agroecological transition, sustainable fisheries and marine ecosystems, recommendations for a healthy, sustainable diet and participatory governance models 2) stakeholder mobilization and participation in territorial projects based on the Living Lab approach and 3) political incidence actions and initiatives. Alimentta is steered by 10 partners - seasoned researchers in their fields (e.g., agroecology, soil health, marine ecosystems, health), a team of technicians, 29 collaborators and a broader community of practice - farmers, SMEs, retailers, consumer groups, policymakers, etc-. Alimentta's biggest strengths rely on its trans-disciplinary approach to sustainable food transition, its vast network of collaborators and its political influence.

Areas of Work

- Agriculture & (Agri-)Food
- Environment/Climate Change
- Research
- Rural

Main Expertise

 Policy Making						
 User & Living Lab Research						

SPAIN

Effective Member

BIRD Living Lab

GAIA

Country: Spain

www.birdcenter.org

Type of Living Lab:

Rural Living Lab
Living Lab as a service
Living testbed

Bird Living Lab is situated at the Biosphere Reserve of Urdaibai (in the Basque Country, North of Spain) in the Urdaibai Bird Centre. Its mission is to co-create, test, and validate ICT products for environmental management and derivate services and scale them up to new markets, as well as create a community of knowledge in environmental management and smart communities, generating a dynamic launching of innovation and new business structures in this area, allowing an emerging sector in which Europe can be leader. Bird Living Lab focuses on the definition and establishment of a Living Lab approach and methodology to speed and strengthen the projects development, as well as for prototyping of the ideas and products, as well as for final users' involvement in the process. Furthermore, it provides a new way of thinking, not just within the project methodology, but also within the project outcomes and potential, re-thinking about the technology developed, giving new uses, and expanding their potential market to new sectors and countries, generating new business opportunities.

Areas of Work

- Circular Economy
- Energy
- Environment/Climate Change
- Policies
- Regulatory Learning
- Rural
- Smart Cities & Regions
- SME & Start-ups
- Social Innovation & Inclusion
- Zero Pollution & Decarbonization

Main Expertise

Adherent Member

Care & Autonomy Living Lab (CALL)

WeMind Cluster

Country: Spain

<https://call.wemindcluster.com/en>

Type of Living Lab:

Living testbed
Living Lab as a service
Research driven Living Lab

Care & Autonomy Living Lab (CALL) is a holistic co-creation space. Its mission is to generate an ecosystem that promotes mental health, neurosciences and ageing through the improvement of the competitiveness of companies and organisations. Innovation, knowledge transfer and collaboration among the different ecosystem agents are fundamental to offer a comprehensive and biopsychosocial support to people.

A realistic approach to healthcare markets through collaborative work, with multidisciplinary and holistic perspectives, is essential for tackling social challenges, promoting also the economic growth of start-ups, SMEs and spin-offs, through an applied technology laboratory.

CALL is a powerful tool for testing products, creating services and shaping public policies.

Areas of Work

- AI and Emerging technologies
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Health & Well Being
- SME & Start-ups
- Social Innovation & Inclusion

Main Expertise

Adherent Member

Citilab Cornellà
Fundació pel Foment de la Societat del Coneixement

Country: Spain

www.citilab.eu

Type of Living Lab:

Citizen laboratory

Citilab is a citizen's laboratory for social and digital innovation, located in Cornellà de Llobregat, Barcelona. It democratizes innovation and develops public policies for citizen social innovation and explores digital impact in creative thinking, design and innovation that emerge from digital culture. Citilab is a mixture between a training centre, a research centre, and a business and social initiative incubator.

Areas of Work

- AI and Emerging technologies
- Circular Economy
- Culture & Creativity (creative sectors)
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Environment/Climate Change
- Gender
- Health & Well Being
- Media
- Mobility
- Regulatory Learning
- Research
- Smart Cities & Regions
- SME & Start-ups
- Social Innovation & Inclusion

Main Expertise

Business Model Innovation	Co-creation Methods & Tools	Governance Models	Impact Assessments	Implementation after Testing	Innovation Strategies	Living Lab Evaluation
Policy Making	Real-life Experimentation	Scaling-up	Service Design	Stakeholder Engagement	User & Living Lab Research	

Effective Member

Colaboratoris Catalunya
i2CAT Foundation

Country: Spain

www.colabscatalunya.cat

Type of Living Lab:

Living testbed
Urban Living Lab
Rural Living Lab
Regional Living Lab
Research driven Living Lab

Mission of I2Cat is to transform Catalonia into a collaboratory, a lab of labs. I2Cat will achieve this mission by: i) contributing qualitatively through tangible projects and initiatives to advancing towards a triple social, digital and green inclusive transition in Catalonia; ii) coordinating the variety of knowledges and capacities of quadruple helix stakeholders' collaborative innovations across all the territories in the countries; iii) aligning local and regional needs and defined challenges with European and global agendas and priorities.

Areas of Work

- Agriculture & (Agri-)Food
- Culture & Creativity (creative sectors)
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Health & Well Being
- Media
- Regulatory Learning
- Rural
- Smart Cities & Regions
- Social Innovation & Inclusion
- Urban

Main Expertise

Business Model Innovation	Co-creation Methods & Tools	Governance Models	Impact Assessments	Implementation after Testing	Innovation Strategies	Living Lab Evaluation
Panel Management	Policy Making	Real-life Experimentation	Scaling-up	Service Design	Stakeholder Engagement	User & Living Lab Research

Adherent Member

Food & Health Living Lab

University of Valencia

Country: Spain

<https://bit.ly/3LFMOXu>

Type of Living Lab:

Research driven Living Lab

Food&HealthLab is a new research concept focused on users and supported in the open innovation and real scenarios. This initiative includes a series of actions to promote health, healthy and sustainable food strategies, nutritional intervention, and improvement of the quality of life within the branches of the University, at a local, national, and international level. It is aimed, on the one hand, to carry out health interventions in an interdisciplinary environment (with dietitians, nutritionists, food technologists, psychologists, geneticists, experts in preventive medicine, physiotherapist and experts in physical and sport activities), to increase the gastronomic and culinary strategies to adapt menus to individuals and/or patients and developing teams, methods and new tools in health environments, nutrition, gastronomy, physical activity and quality of life with applicability to society.

Areas of Work

- Agriculture & (Agri-)Food
- AI and Emerging technologies
- Culture & Creativity (creative sectors)
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Environment/Climate Change
- Health & Well Being
- Industries & Manufacturing
- Media
- Rural
- SME & Start-ups
- Social Innovation & Inclusion
- Water (Blue economy)
- Zero Pollution & Decarbonization

Main Expertise

Business Model Innovation	Co-creation Methods & Tools	Governance Models	Impact Assessments	Implementation after Testing	Innovation Strategies	Living Lab Evaluation
Panel Management	Policy Making	Real-life Experimentation	Scaling-up	Service Design	Stakeholder Engagement	User & Living Lab Research

FUNDACIÓN ÉPICA
LA FURA DELS BAUS

Adherent Member

Fundación Épica La Fura dels Baus

Country: Spain

www.epicalab.com

Type of Living Lab:

Research driven Living Lab

Epica has the horizontal collaboration between science, technology, and humanities, as the catalyser for disruptive R+D+I in the new digital era. Thanks to the experience gathered in last 40 years of history of its patrons La Fura dels Baus, Epica has distilled a methodology where, performing arts is the vehicle for these new R+D+I processes, enabling to: i) promote the knowledge transfer between disciplines and to civil society; ii) actively engage into the same ecosystem and processes all quadruple helix agents, through common language; iii) establish the proper sandbox for co-design, experiment, develop, validate, and experience potential future realities and situations (fake realities), new technologies, products and/or processes, through anticipatory arts. Through the use of performing arts, Epica is able to create a neutral environment for cross-research and mutual learning between disciplines and between different players (citizenship, researchers, institutions, companies).

Areas of Work

- Culture & Creativity (creative sectors)
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Environment/Climate Change
- Health & Well Being
- Industries & Manufacturing
- Media
- Social Innovation & Inclusion

Main Expertise

Business Model Innovation	Co-creation Methods & Tools	Impact Assessments	Implementation after Testing	Innovation Strategies	Panel Management	Real-life Experimentation
Scaling-up	Service Design	Stakeholder Engagement	User & Living Lab Research			

Adherent Member

Galician Network of Health Living Labs

Axencia Galega de Coñecemento en Saúde (ACIS)

Country: Spain

www.labsaude.sergas.gal

Type of Living Lab:

Living testbed

The Galician Network of Health Living Labs - LABSAÚDE, is an initiative promoted by the Galician Health Service and ACIS that will convert Galician Hospitals and Health Centres into authentic testing laboratories for new solutions/products or services related to health and thus create an ecosystem of multidisciplinary and multisectoral co-creation focused on the user. The first Living Lab of the Network was created in the University Hospital Complex of Ourense (CHUOU), which has been enlarged and a space has been reserved for the development of an experimental hospitalization, by defining an innovative functional model and providing equipment and facilities for different Living Lab scenarios in which health research and innovation studies will be developed.

Areas of Work

- AI and Emerging technologies
- Health & Well Being
- Smart Cities & Regions
- Social Innovation & Inclusion

Adherent Member

Healthcare Living Lab Catalonia

Leitat

Country: Spain

www.healthcarelivinglab.cat

Type of Living Lab:

Living testbed
Living Lab as a service

The Healthcare Living Lab Catalonia (HCLLC) is a Living Lab specialized in the health and social fields. Its mission is to bring together healthcare centres, technological centres and Living Labs throughout Catalonia, and connect them to innovation entities and innovative people, facilitating the prototyping, testing and validation of their solutions based on its own methodology and in a fast and efficient way, maximizing the results obtained. The HCLLC offers its services to advise and methodologically guide start-ups, SMEs and companies that want to prototype, test and/or validate innovative solutions in real-life environments and with end users in the fields of medical devices, in vitro diagnostics, and digital health. It is an initiative of Leitat that has the mission of turning Catalonia into a Living Lab of reference and, for this reason, it has a vast network of collaborating entities; on the one hand, the main health centres and innovation referents throughout the country and, on the other hand, the main associations of health and social centres in the country.

Areas of Work

- AI and Emerging technologies
- Health & Well Being
- SME & Start-ups
- Social Innovation & Inclusion

Main Expertise

Adherent Member

IDEA LIVING LAB

IDEA: INNOVACIÓN Y DESARROLLO ASISTENCIAL

Country: Spain

www.ideainnovacion.com

Type of Living Lab:

Living testbed
Urban Living Lab
Rural Living Lab
Living Lab as a service
Research driven Living Lab

The Idea Living Lab serves as a central hub in the open health ecosystem, focused on enhancing the quality of life for the elderly. Our work occurs in real environments, aiming to improve without disruption. We research, share knowledge, and create innovative products and services to elevate elderly life. We follow a co-creation, co-design, and person-centered care approach.

Our transdisciplinary technical team, consisting of geriatricians, psychogerontologists, physiotherapists, economists, managers, occupational therapists, social workers, marketing, and business experts, addresses diverse elderly needs across contexts.

Collaboration spans local to European levels, involving universities, elderly associations, research centers, public administrations, and private enterprises. We innovate empathetically, letting the elderly determine the feasibility of innovations based on real needs.

Areas of Work

- AI and Emerging technologies
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Health & Well Being
- SME & Start-ups
- Social Innovation & Inclusion

Main Expertise

Business Model Innovation	Co-creation Methods & Tools	Governance Models	Impact Assessments	Implementation after Testing	Innovation Strategies	Living Lab Evaluation
Panel Management	Real-life Experimentation	Scaling-up	Service Design	Stakeholder Engagement	User & Living Lab Research	

Adherent Member

INTERiORS Living Lab
CENFIM FURNISHINGS CLUSTER

Country: Spain

www.cenfim.org

Type of Living Lab:

Living Lab as a service

INTERiORS LIVING LAB by CENFIM Furnishings Cluster involves in a straightforward manner more than 160 affiliated companies, including home and contract interiors products manufacturers, retailers and auxiliary industries motivated by innovation from furniture, home textiles, lighting, bath, paving and other sectors (covering all the interiors value chain). The Living Lab has a total outreach of more than 2.600 companies across Spain and many other entities across the European Union.

Areas of Work

- AI and Emerging technologies
- Circular Economy
- Culture & Creativity (creative sectors)
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Health & Well Being
- Industries & Manufacturing
- SME & Start-ups
- Social Innovation & Inclusion

Main Expertise

Business Model Innovation	Co-creation Methods & Tools	Impact Assessments	Implementation after Testing	Innovation Strategies	Living Lab Evaluation	Panel Management
Policy Making	Real-life Experimentation	Scaling-up	Service Design	Stakeholder Engagement	User & Living Lab Research	

Adherent Member

IoT Smart Santander Living Lab

Universidad de Cantabria

Country: Spain

Type of Living Lab:

Urban Living Lab
Living Lab as a service
Research driven Living Lab

The IoT SmartSantander Living Lab is aiming at providing an open innovation ecosystem in which companies, research centre and public bodies can undertake new initiatives upon co-creation. Last but not least, citizens leverage on this Living Lab for making a reality the paradigm of data economy.

Areas of Work

- AI and Emerging technologies
- Circular Economy
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Mobility
- Rural
- Smart Cities & Regions
- Social Innovation & Inclusion

Main Expertise

 Living Lab Evaluation						
 User & Living Lab Research						

DIGITAL GASTRONOMY LAB

Adherent Member

LABE Digital Gastronomy Lab

Basque Culinary Center Fundazioa

Country: Spain

www.labe-dgl.com

Type of Living Lab:

Urban Living Lab
Living Lab as a service
Living testbed

LABE's mission is to drive the digital transformation of gastronomy towards a healthy, sustainable, and delicious future through real context experimentation, innovation and co-creation of digital tools and tech solutions. Main focus areas are: process optimization and automation throughout gastronomy and food supply chain; smart equipment design and development; gastronomy and food experience in the Web 3.0.

Areas of Work

- Agriculture & (Agri-)Food
- Circular Economy
- Culture & Creativity (creative sectors)
- Health & Well Being
- SME & Start-ups

Main Expertise

 Living Lab Evaluation						
 User & Living Lab Research						

Effective Member

Library Living Lab

Computer Vision Center

Country: Spain

www.librarylivinglab.com

Type of Living Lab:

Urban Living Lab
Research driven Living Lab

Library Living Lab explores how technology can transform the experiences of people with culture. This is done through different types of activities and events following a number lines of work. These lines of work are aligned with current, real social challenges related to the cultural context that the library provides. These challenges are periodically updated by the Library Living Panel, and they provide a very flexible framework for prioritised actions of different types, such as periodical activities, open workshops, public demonstrations of prototypes, scientific experiments open to the citizen participation, open debates, and innovation projects with Public Institutions (such as research centres, universities, foundations) and Companies. The Living Lab Pilot running in Sant Cugat for 5 years from its opening in 2015 reached the end of its test phase in 2020, and it is now entering in a new phase, scaling it up to the Barcelona’s Provincial Council’s Network of 203+ Public Libraries.

Areas of Work

- Agriculture & (Agri-)Food
- AI and Emerging technologies
- Culture & Creativity (creative sectors)
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Health & Well Being
- Industries & Manufacturing
- Media
- Mobility
- Policies
- Regulatory Learning
- Rural
- Smart Cities & Regions
- SME & Start-ups
- Social Innovation & Inclusion

Main Expertise

Business Model Innovation	Co-creation Methods & Tools	Governance Models	Impact Assessments	Implementation after Testing	Innovation Strategies	Living Lab Evaluation
Policy Making	Real-life Experimentation	Scaling-up	Service Design	Stakeholder Engagement	User & Living Lab Research	

Adherent Member

LIVING LAB ECONOMÍA SOCIAL

ASATA (AGRUPACIÓN DE SOCIEDADES ASTURIANAS DE TRABAJO ASOCIADO Y ECONOMÍA SOCIAL)

Country: Spain

<https://asata.es>

Type of Living Lab:

Living Lab as a service

The LLES Living Lab for Social Economy is focused on social innovation and it is a Living Lab with an innovative approach that involves collaboration among different key agents, in order to design, develop, test, and validate innovative solutions that allow the transformation of long- term care, with the aim of ensuring quality and sustainable care over time.

Areas of Work

- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Health & Well Being
- Rural
- SME & Start-ups
- Social Innovation & Inclusion
- Urban
- Other areas of work

Adherent Member

Living Lab Social in real environment

Ageing Social Lab

Country: Spain

www.ageinglab.org

Living Lab Social in real environment offers a comprehensive and direct service providing customized solutions both research projects and in the development as innovation for products and services for the elderly, in order to adapt these products and services to their needs. Living Lab is a real-life test and experimentation environment where users and producers co-create innovations. It seeks a strong user and stakeholder-driven approach and commitment to iterative design, test and validation of solutions. In this sense, the activities of the Living Lab revolve around: i)co-design users, suppliers and designers in developing the concept and definition of the solution; ii) participation and involvement of end users in the process for action research; iii) exploration of ideas and needs for the discovery of new uses or adaptation of resources; iv) the application of live scenarios within the user communities; v) evaluation of concepts, products and services. Living Lab Social in real environment is able to bring together and engage numerous stakeholders in the aging process, by creating synergies through professional, collaborative and expert networks. The development the Living Lab is made with character intergenerational, involving formal and informal caregivers, professionals and institutions in related sectors to improve the quality of life of the aging process (social, health, tourism, knowledge, etc.).

Adherent Member

Medialab UGR: Research Laboratory for Digital Culture and Society

University of Granada (Social Innovation Vicerectorate)

Country: Spain

www.librarylivinglab.com

Type of Living Lab:

Urban Living Lab
Living Lab as a service
Research driven Living Lab

MediaLab UGR is conceived as a meeting space for the analysis, research and dissemination of the possibilities that digital technologies generate in culture and society in general.

Areas of Work

- Culture & Creativity (creative sectors)
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Media
- Regulatory Learning
- Rural
- Social Innovation & Inclusion

Main Expertise

Co-creation Methods & Tools Governance Models Impact Assessments Innovation Strategies Panel Management Policy Making Real-life Experimentation User & Living Lab Research

Effective Member

MINDLab

INTRAS Foundation

Country: Spain

www.intras.es/investigacion-desarrollo-de-tecnologias-e-innovacion

Type of Living Lab:

Urban Living Lab
Rural Living Lab
Living Lab as a service
Living testbed
Research driven Living Lab

MIND-LAB operates in a quadruple helix innovation ecosystem, focusing on the Castilla y León and Madrid Regions for social-health care, mental health, longevity for vulnerable populations through co-creation, devoted to high-quality research and committed to Open and Responsible Innovation, engaging the public and patients in Participatory and Value-Sensitive Design. Aims to address existing and emerging needs improving social-healthcare services by developing methods and products with researchers, clinicians, technologists, engaging all stakeholders needed. MINDLab focuses in designing, developing, testing: VR/AR for cognitive and multisensory interventions and wellbeing; technologies for neuropsychological assessment, stimulation, rehabilitation, early detection of mild cognitive impairment and to enhance QoL in palliative care; social robotics in care contexts; sensor-enhanced environments to monitor and promote independent living; research in real environments and LL methodologies.

Areas of Work

- AI and Emerging technologies
- Culture & Creativity (creative sectors)
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Health & Well Being
- Policies
- Research
- Rural
- Smart Cities & Regions
- SME & Start-ups

Main Expertise

Business Model Innovation	Co-creation Methods & Tools	Governance Models	Impact Assessments	Implementation after Testing	Innovation Strategies	Living Lab Evaluation
Panel Management	Policy Making	Real-life Experimentation	Scaling-up	Service Design	Stakeholder Engagement	User & Living Lab Research

Adherent Member

Neàpolis

Neàpolis

Country: Spain

www.neapolis.cat

Type of Living Lab:

Urban Living Lab
Living Lab as a service
Living testbed

An Innovation Agency for technology, communication and creativity, Neàpolis is a Public Innovation Agency for ICT, the multimedia sector, creativity, and entrepreneurship. It offers a space for experimentation, incubation, and growth for the city's entrepreneurial community, promoting innovation and collaboration. For all of them, coworking and business incubator services are offered as well as connectivity, support, and advice while facilitating its insertion itinerary in the labour market. Since 2006, Vilanova i la Geltrú and its territory of influence have established themselves to promote the innovative ecosystem, ICT businesses, the media, and the creative industries.

Areas of Work

- AI and Emerging technologies
- Culture & Creativity (creative sectors)
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Environment/Climate Change
- Health & Well Being
- Media
- Mobility
- Smart Cities & Regions
- SME & Start-ups
- Social Innovation & Inclusion
- Urban
- Other areas of work

Main Expertise

Business Model Innovation	Co-creation Methods & Tools	Governance Models	Impact Assessments	Implementation after Testing	Innovation Strategies	Policy Making
Service Design	Stakeholder Engagement	User & Living Lab Research				

Adherent Member

NEUROLAB, ADACEN Living Lab

ADACEN, (Navarra Cerebral Damage Association)

Country: Spain

www.adacen.org

Type of Living Lab:

Living testbed
Research driven Living Lab

The Adacen Living Lab is an area of research and testing which exists to help patients, designers, researchers and firms to work together on innovations and test products and developments focused on neurological rehabilitation and the promotion of self-sufficiency. Its object is the creation of new services, products and infrastructures that are appropriate for the current needs that the challenge of old age and neurological rehabilitation require.

On being set up and for its subsequent development, the living lab has had its own methodology and has taken on staff that is specialized in neurological rehabilitation and the treatment of the elderly and people with disabilities, who are trained in the processes of innovations centered on the person.

Adacen Living Lab is led by Adacen together with the Public University of Navarra and the Social Innovation Unit of the Government of Navarra and was incorporated in November 2019 to the European Network of Living Labs (ENoLL), being the first member of ENoLL in Navarra.

Areas of Work

- AI and Emerging technologies
- Health & Well Being
- Social Innovation & Inclusion

Main Expertise

Adherent Member

OZEAN LIVING LAB

ESKILARA S KOOP TXIKIA

Country: Spain

www.ozeanlab.tech

Type of Living Lab:

Urban Living Lab
Rural Living Lab
Living testbed
Living Lab as a service

Ozean Living Lab is a large-scale open innovation lab to attract companies and promote projects through innovation in strategic sustainable projects. Ozean Living Lab was born to face territorial challenges by promoting the natural environment Urdaibai's Biosphere Reserve and the competitiveness of the companies in the area through open innovation. A regional strategy with an international perspective: "Improve the quality of life through environmental, social and economic credentials, based on the multifunctional use of Urdaibai's natural capitals". Its 4 key objectives are: i) protect ecosystems state and biodiversity; ii) improve ecosystem functioning and promote ecosystem services; iii) promote societal wellbeing and health; iv) support the development of a green economy, and sustainable land and water management.

Areas of Work

- Circular Economy
- Culture & Creativity (creative sectors)
- Environment/Climate Change
- Health & Well Being
- Smart Cities & Regions
- SME & Start-ups
- Social Innovation & Inclusion
- Water (Blue economy)

Main Expertise

Adherent Member

Social Digital Lab (Suara)

Suara Serveis SCCL

Country: Spain

<https://www.suara.coop/en/innovacio>

Type of Living Lab:

Living Lab as a service

Social Digital Lab represents an innovative concept tailored to the new needs of today's world, where technological experimentation, research and support for social and digital innovation projects are the cornerstones. It is a user-centric open-innovation platform based on a systematic approach to co-creation, which integrates research and innovation processes in communities and real-life environments. Suara Cooperativa's Living Lab emerges as an innovative concept for research, development and innovation, focusing on involving users in all phases of this process, generating a huge potential for the creation of ICT-based products and services, which is why it is necessary to bring all relevant actors (public and private) together in a collaborative approach.

Areas of Work

- Circular Economy
- Health & Well Being
- Social Innovation & Inclusion

Main Expertise

Adherent Member

SSI Living Lab

Servicios Sociales Integrados, S. Coop.

Country: Spain

www.gruposssi.es/homecarelab-gruposssi-innovacion/#ssi-living-lab

Type of Living Lab:

Living Lab as a service
Living testbed

Servicios Sociales Integrados, S. Coop. (Grupo SSI) is a cooperative company set up in Bilbao in 1986, to respond to the social needs of people in situations of dependence and social vulnerability, and their families, in Euskadi. S.S.I. The Group and the entities that belong to it (Aurrerantz, S. Coop. de Iniciativa Social, Aurrerantz Asociación, Euskarri, S. Coop. Empresa de Inserción and Home Care Lab, S. Coop.) promoted the creation of the Living Lab to enrich and strengthen the innovation capacities of the Group around ageing and dependence and improve its competitiveness. Specifically, Home Care Lab, S. Coop., the Group's R&D&I business unit, is one of the most important actors that make up the Living Lab. Home Care Lab, S. Coop. is boosted by the Living Lab, experimenting, and carrying out drills of the daily activities dependent people, the carers, and their families face. The Living Lab is a pioneering infrastructure

in Euskadi that attempts to simulate the different rooms of a home with advanced technology. It has 100 sqm and adapted beds and baths, a hydraulic motor cranes, a modular kitchen, etc., resources that are equipped with technological advances that make it easier to care for elderly dependent people. It also has user friendly touch screen computers that avoid having to use a mouse and keyboard for people with reduced mobility, and that using software allow carrying out videoconferences. Its most innovating technological characteristic is a hydraulic motor crane system that hung from the ceiling can move the dependent users from their wheelchair to any room in the simulated home.

Areas of Work

- Health & Well Being
- Social Innovation & Inclusion

Main Expertise

Adherent Member

UAB Smart Campus Living Lab

University Autònoma of Barcelona

Country: Spain

<https://bit.ly/3WnlYiv>

Type of Living Lab:

Research driven Living Lab

The campus has become a primary area for experimentation, innovation and demonstration of new technologies and methodologies, and also an incubator/accelerator for different types of projects and initiatives, which can then be applied in the neighboring municipalities.

Areas of Work

- Agriculture & (Agri-)Food
- AI and Emerging technologies
- Circular Economy
- Culture & Creativity (creative sectors)
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Energy
- Environment/Climate Change
- Health & Well Being
- Rural
- Smart Cities & Regions
- SME & Start-ups
- Social Innovation & Inclusion
- Urban
- Water (Blue economy)
- Zero Pollution & Decarbonization

Main Expertise

Business Model Innovation	Co-creation Methods & Tools	Governance Models	Impact Assessments	Implementation after Testing	Innovation Strategies	Living Lab Evaluation
Panel Management	Policy Making	Real-life Experimentation	Scaling-up	Service Design	Stakeholder Engagement	User & Living Lab Research

Adherent Member

Valencia Living Lab - People Innovating for People

Fundación de la Comunidad Valenciana para la Promoción Estratégica, el Desarrollo y la Innovación

Country: Spain

<https://www.lasnaves.com>

Type of Living Lab:

Urban Living Lab

The aim of this LL is to make Valencia a laboratory city by creating experimentation spaces, public infrastructures and processes designed to experiment with new solutions, services and products that are developed by innovative ecosystem, as well as by the citizenship, and which require testing in real conditions. Within its scope, Valenica LL has been working for years in the development of this experimentative city vision, to which it is now possible to contribute with the following three concrete assets. 1) Las NAVES + La HARINERA Living Lab: the conversion of the public innovation centre in Valencia into a living lab focused on co-creating innovation that improves people's lives. 2) URBAN REGULATORY SANDBOX of the city of Valencia, which is one of the first local-scale regulatory sandboxes to be created in Spain. 3) TEF – TESTING & EXPERIMENTATION FACILITY, which will be one of the three laboratories to be set up in Europe, in this case focusing on AI.

Areas of Work

- Agriculture & (Agri-)Food
- AI and Emerging technologies
- Culture & Creativity (creative sectors)
- Energy
- Environment/Climate Change
- Health & Well Being
- Mobility
- Policies
- Regulatory Learning
- Rural
- Smart Cities & Regions
- SME & Start-ups
- Social Innovation & Inclusion
- Soil
- Zero Pollution & Decarbonization

Main Expertise

Business Model Innovation	Co-creation Methods & Tools	Governance Models	Impact Assessments	Implementation after Testing	Innovation Strategies	Living Lab Evaluation
Panel Management	Policy Making	Real-life Experimentation	Scaling-up	Service Design	Stakeholder Engagement	User & Living Lab Research

Adherent Member

Botnia Living Lab

Luleå University of Technology

Country: Sweden

www.ltu.se

Type of Living Lab:

Living testbed
Urban Living Lab
Rural Living Lab
Research driven Living Lab

Botnia Living Lab is a world leading environment for user-centric research, development, and innovation (RDI), supported by innovative methods, tools and experts and is also one of the founders and a member of the European Network of Living Labs (ENoLL). Botnia Living Lab has a particular interest in Living Lab research as it is hosted by Luleå University of Technology and several researchers with high academic expertise and experiences are contributing to the projects that Botnia Living Lab is involved in. The projects are focused on digital innovation and transformation, smart cities and regions, urban and rural Living Labs, sustainability as well as education, in both national and international levels.

Areas of Work

- Agriculture & (Agri-)Food
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Environment/Climate Change
- Health & Well Being
- Research
- Rural
- Smart Cities & Regions
- Social Innovation & Inclusion
- Urban

Main Expertise

Co-creation
Methods & Tools

Governance
Models

Impact
Assessments

Implementation
after Testing

Innovation
Strategies

Living Lab
Evaluation

Panel
Management

Real-life
Experimentation

Scaling-up

Service Design

Stakeholder
Engagement

User & Living Lab
Research

SWEDEN

Adherent Member

HSB Living Lab

HSB Göteborg

Country: Sweden

www.hsblivinglab.com

Type of Living Lab:

Living testbed
Urban Living Lab

HSB Living Lab is a journey towards future housing. The project tests completely new technological and architectural innovations over a period of 10 years. The building, located at Chalmers Campus Johanneberg in Gothenburg, is so much more than a house – it is a Living Laboratory where research can be done in a way never done before. HSB Living Lab is a movable four-storey building and was ready for occupancy on June 1, 2016. Three of the floors are housing for students and visiting researchers and on the ground floor there are collaboration rooms with offices, conference rooms, showrooms for research projects, and a modern laundry studio. The accommodation in HSB Living Lab today consists of 29 apartments where tenants live in an ever-changing and evaluated environment, all while the research is ongoing. HSB Living Lab is run by 12 partners to create a solid collaboration arena for new knowledge with a focus on social, economic, and environmental sustainability.

Areas of Work

- Circular Economy
- Energy
- Environment/climate change
- Health & Wellbeing
- Mobility
- Research
- Smart Cities & Regions
- Urban
- Water (Blue economy)
- Zero Pollution & Decarbonisation

Main Expertise

Business Model Innovation, Co-creation Methods & Tools, Governance Models, Impact Assessments, Implementation after Testing, Innovation Strategies, Living Lab Evaluation, Real-life Experimentation, Scaling-up, Stakeholder Engagement, User & Living Lab Research

Adherent Member

Living Lab at Mälardalen University

Mälardalen University

Country: Sweden

Type of Living Lab:

Living testbed
Research driven Living Lab

The projects managed by MDU Living Lab strives to create an awareness of the co-creation process as such, in developing education programs, courses or research and students' project. MDU Living Lab aims to further develop and document new methods for co-creation within academic education and research.

Areas of Work

- Culture & Creativity (creative sectors)
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Health & Well Being
- Industries & Manufacturing
- Social Innovation & Inclusion

Main Expertise

Co-creation Methods & Tools, Impact Assessments, Implementation after Testing, Innovation Strategies, Living Lab Evaluation, Panel Management, Real-life Experimentation, Stakeholder Engagement, User & Living Lab Research

Adherent Member

Småland Regional Living Lab

**Department of Design,
Linnaeus University**

Country: Sweden

www.lnu.se/en/research/searchresearch/smaland-living-lab

Type of Living Lab:

Research driven Living Lab

Småland Living Lab is about finding and building on synergies between social, cultural, economic, and ecological dimensions of sustainability. Through it experimentation, learning and change, education and inspiration happen simultaneously. The vision of Småland Living Lab is that it will connect a range of initiatives in the remit of sustainability within the region, for knowledge exchange, power, visibility, and also create models for other regions. Småland Living Lab works at the local and regional level to support adaption to a circular economy, and to meet and exceed the UN Sustainable Development Goals. Småland Living Lab uses meta design approaches and tools developed to prompt synergy in transdisciplinary collaborations.

Adherent Member

The Swedish Living Lab on Vehicle and Transport ICT

Country: Sweden

The Swedish Living Lab on Vehicle and Transport ICT (SVT-LL) is a competitive Living Lab for user-driven development of automotive and transport applications and services. The objective of the SVT-LL is to leverage Sweden's strong cluster of automotive and transport firms through the development, adoption, and use of co-creation approaches to product and service innovation. SVT-LL is coordinated by the Viktoria Institute.

Areas of Work

- Culture & Creativity (creative sectors)
- Environment/Climate Change
- Social Innovation & Inclusion

Main Expertise

Adherent Member

Ecopol Living Lab & ecovillages Romandie

APTES - Association pour la Promotion de la Transdisciplinarité et de l'Entrepreneuriat social

Country: Switzerland

www.ecopol.net/enoll

Type of Living Lab:

Rural Living Lab
Ecovillage
Living Lab as a service
Research driven Living Lab

Since 1993, the R&D team develops and facilitates ecovillage intergenerational and intercultural dialogue to incubate intentional communities dedicated to deep ecology and energetical sobriety. The Living Lab manages 3 eco-centres gathering families, artists, social entrepreneurs, seniors, refugees, academic researchers, and public officers.

Areas of Work

- Circular Economy
- Culture & Creativity (creative sectors)
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Environment/Climate Change
- Smart Cities & Regions
- SME & Start-ups
- Social Innovation & Inclusion
- Zero Pollution & Decarbonization

Main Expertise

 Panel Management						
 User & Living Lab Research						

SWITZERLAND

Effective Member

**Energy Living Lab
HES-SO**

Country: Switzerland

www.energylivinglab.com

Type of Living Lab:

Urban Living Lab

The Energy Living Lab Association (ELLA) has been created in 2020 as a spin-off to replicate, disseminate and communicate Living Lab approaches in the energy field. It supports an ecosystem of actors in using the methods and tools and invites people and institutions from the Public, Private, Governmental, Academic sectors and civil society to co-design solutions for Energy Decarbonisation. The HES-SO research team works on applied research, methods, and tools to further develop the knowledge on applying Living Lab methods in the energy field. Designing research projects, publishing scientific articles, developing a network of researchers, teaching Living Labs, open innovation and social innovation are main activities within the Energy Living Lab @HES-SO.

Areas of Work

- Circular Economy
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Energy
- Environment/Climate Change
- Mobility
- Smart Cities & Regions
- SME & Start-ups
- Social Innovation & Inclusion
- Water (Blue economy)
- Zero Pollution & Decarbonization

Main Expertise

Business Model Innovation	Co-creation Methods & Tools	Governance Models	Impact Assessments	Implementation after Testing	Innovation Strategies	Living Lab Evaluation
Panel Management	Real-life Experimentation	Scaling-up	Service Design	Stakeholder Engagement	User & Living Lab Research	

Adherent Member

**FiBL On - farm
Living Labs**

FiBL

Country: Switzerland

www.fibl.org

Type of Living Lab:

Research driven Living Lab

The Living Lab is part of the project ROADMAP (Rethinking of Antimicrobial Decision-Systems in the Management of Animal Production) which will foster transitions towards prudent antimicrobial use (AMU) in animal production in a large variety of contexts, by favouring a rethinking antimicrobial decision system all along the food supply chain.

Areas of Work

- Agriculture & (Agri-)Food

Main Expertise

Impact Assessments	Implementation after Testing	Innovation Strategies	Stakeholder Engagement	User & Living Lab Research
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Adherent Member

Genève Lab

State of Geneva

Country: Switzerland

www.ge.ch/dossier/geneve-lab

Type of Living Lab:

Living Lab as a service

Genève Lab supports the public administration of the State of Geneva in the transformation induced by the challenges of the digital age. This consists of helping project leaders to adopt a user-centred approach, to work in a collaborative, multidisciplinary manner and by opening up to our ecosystem, as well as to favour prototyping and iteration.

Areas of Work

- Social Innovation & Inclusion
- Other areas of work

Main Expertise

Adherent Member

iHomeLab (iHL)

Hochschule Luzern
Technik & Architektur

Country: Switzerland

www.ihomelab.ch

Type of Living Lab:

Research driven Living Lab

The iHomeLab Living Lab of the Lucerne University of Applied Sciences (LUAS) is the leading research centre for building intelligence in Switzerland. Connected within a broad network of experts, it also engages in international initiatives to further develop these fields, contributes to scientific conferences and trade fairs and actively takes part in shaping new standards and technologies being a member of several technology standards organisations and professional unions (e.g. ZigBee Alliance, KNX Scientific, IEEE, IPv6 Swiss Council, AALOA, 4E, terzStiftung). Together with its industrial partners, the iHomeLab Living Lab team conducts applied research to increase the energy efficiency, security and comfort in residential as well as commercial buildings. The research strategy focuses on the three research areas of energy efficiency (EE), ambient assisted living (AAL) and human building interaction (HBI) under the roof of the metaresearch topic “The Building as a System” at the Lucerne University of Applied Sciences.

Areas of Work

- Agriculture & (Agri-)Food
- Energy
- Health & Well Being
- Research
- Smart Cities & Regions

Main Expertise

Adherent Member

Living Lab for Special Needs
HES-SO Valais-Wallis

Country: Switzerland

<https://frh-fondation.ch/en/living-lab/>

Type of Living Lab:

Living testbed
Living Lab as a service
Research driven Living Lab

Founded in 2018, in collaboration with the HES-SO Valais-Wallis, the Living Lab for Special Needs aims to create an innovation platform for disability in the broadest sense. It acts as a forum to exchange between different partners on disability-related issues, with the aim of developing new technological solutions and/or services that can help them. It is a co-creation and innovation network, a space to exchange bringing together people with disabilities, scientists, companies and all other people interested in collaborating in the field of disability and in the co-creation of new innovative solutions. Living Lab Handicap is accredited by the European Network of Living Labs.

Areas of Work

- AI and Emerging technologies
- Health & Well Being
- Social Innovation & Inclusion
- Other areas of work

Main Expertise

Adherent Member

Lugano Living Lab
City of Lugano

Country: Switzerland

www.luganolivinglab.ch

Type of Living Lab:

Urban Living Lab

The need for a modern quality management of public affairs, based on data, facts and figures and functional for the vision and strategy defined by the Municipality, has led to the creation of the Lugano Living Lab operating platform, as a concrete response aimed at encouraging innovation to further improve the quality of life of citizens and the attractiveness of the region.

Areas of Work

- Culture & Creativity (creative sectors)
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Energy
- Health & Well Being
- Mobility
- Social Innovation & Inclusion

Main Expertise

Adherent Member

Mobile Communications and Computing for Life Quality

Quality of Life Technologies Lab (University of Geneva)

Country: Switzerland

<https://www.qualityoflifetechnologies.com>

Type of Living Lab:

Research driven Living Lab

Quality of Life (QoL) Technologies Lab's mission is to responsibly unleash the power of data to benefit the quality of life of all individuals. More specifically, the Lab's mission is to design, develop and evaluate advanced computational models and algorithms embedded within emerging mobile technologies to assess individuals' life quality as it unfolds naturally over time and in context and improves it at all stages of life. The mQoL Living Lab supports the research goals of the QoL Lab by serving as an umbrella for study participants' enrolment and continuous engagement.

Areas of Work

- Gender
- Health & Well Being
- Mobility
- Researchg
- Social Innovation & Inclusion

Main Expertise

mobility lab

Adherent Member

Mobility Lab CH

Swiss Post Ltd, Corporate Development, CEO Corporate Services

Country: Switzerland

www.mobilitylab.ch

Type of Living Lab:

Urban Living Lab
Research driven Living Lab

The challenges in the public space, particularly in the area of transport and mobility, will increase in the coming years. The Mobility Lab wants to provide innovative solutions. Since 2014, the Mobility Lab in Sion-Valais has brought together the Federal Institute of Technology Lausanne (EPFL), the University of Applied Sciences HES-SO Valais-Wallis, the Canton of Valais, the City of Sion and Swiss Post. Together, these partners develop innovative ideas and test solutions in the public space in Sion and its region, particularly in the field of mobility.

Areas of Work

- Circular Economy
- Energy
- Mobility
- Smart Cities & Regions
- Urban
- Zero Pollution & Decarbonization

Main Expertise

Adherent Member

Senior-Lab

Institut et Haute Ecole de la Santé La Source; HEIG-VD; ECAL (HES-SO)

Country: Switzerland

www.senior-lab.ch

Type of Living Lab:

Research driven Living Lab

The senior-lab is an innovation and research platform dedicated to the quality of life of the elderly. The interdisciplinary approach is in its DNA as it was created by three schools of applied sciences, each one specialized in very different, but complementary, subjects (management, engineering, health, art, and design). The Living Lab team strongly believes that no successful innovation is possible without the involvement of the end-users already from the first steps of the process. For this reason, it develops all projects with a community of senior citizens, in a user-driven mindset. The elderly share their experiences, expectations, and aspirations to co-create products, services and technologies that will concretely match their needs.

Areas of Work

- Health & Well Being
- Research
- Social Innovation & Inclusion

Main Expertise

Adherent Member

Smart Living Lab

EPFL (Ecole polytechnique fédérale de Lausanne, Switzerland)

Country: Switzerland

www.smartlivinglab.ch

Type of Living Lab:

Research driven Living Lab

The Smart Living Lab is a research and development centre for the future of the built environment. It focuses on carbon footprint, energy systems, construction technology, digital transformation, comfort, and well-being of users (IEQ, user-building interactions). Interdisciplinary research projects are pursued with experiments carried out in real-life conditions.

Areas of Work

- Circular Economy
- Energy
- Environment/Climate Change
- Health & Well Being
- Smart Cities & Regions
- Water (Blue economy)
- Zero Pollution & Decarbonization

Main Expertise

Adherent Member

Swiss Food Research

Swiss Food Research

Country: Switzerland

<https://www.swissfoodresearch.ch/de/>

Type of Living Lab:

Living testbed
Living Lab as a service
Research driven Living Lab

Swiss Food Research (SFR) is Switzerland's largest Agro-Food and Nutrition Innovation Network. Together with its 200+ members from academia, industry, and society, SFR catalyses holistic innovation along the entire value chain to support transformation toward a future-oriented agro food & nutrition system. Swiss Food Research supports projects from the problem up to market readiness in a neutral, confidential, and independent manner. This support ranges from knowledge transfer, sparring, workshops, to funding support, to market testing within real warm data environment.

Areas of Work

- Agriculture & (Agri-)Food
- Circular Economy
- SME & Start-ups

Main Expertise

 Living Lab Evaluation						
 User & Living Lab Research						

TAIWAN

Effective Member

Taiwan Living Lab

Institute for Information Industry

Country: Taiwan

www.livinglabs.com.tw/en/

Type of Living Lab:

Urban Living Lab
Living testbed
Living Lab as a service
Research driven Living Lab

The Taiwan Living Lab operated by Institute for Information Industry is committed to three core values: innovation, compassion, and effectiveness. Institute for Information Industry will follow a well-designed blueprint of services to choose the target group to serve and design various experiments to evaluate the performances of new technological services. Its mission is to assist domestic businesses to proceed the PoC, PoS and PoB projects in the validation phase of service concept to reduce the potential risks for lacking proper understanding of the market, and to raise the chance to succeed in IT enabled service providing businesses.

Areas of Work

- AI and Emerging technologies
- Culture & Creativity (creative sectors)
- Health & Well Being
- Industries & Manufacturing
- Mobility
- Smart Cities & Regions
- SME & Start-ups
- Social Innovation & Inclusion

Main Expertise

 Living Lab Evaluation						
 User & Living Lab Research						

TUNISIA

Adherent Member

DIGIART LIVING LAB

DigiArt Living Lab

Tunisian Association of Creative Technology

Country: Tunisia

www.dall4all.org

Type of Living Lab:

Urban Living Lab
Living Lab as a service
Research driven Living Lab

Digiart Living Lab (DALL) is a creative platform for social and open innovation. The DALL is a space to welcome the African talents wishing to develop their creative spirit and wanting to produce creative, innovative projects, having a social impact, and using creative and digital technologies (3D, Video game, Virtual Reality, Augmented Reality, IoT, etc.). DALL's main mission is to support the community of young people and talents passionate about creative and digital technologies, to organize events and to carry out projects that contribute to the development of the digital arts sector in African Continent.

Areas of Work

- AI and Emerging technologies
- Culture & Creativity (creative sectors)
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Health & Well Being
- Industries & Manufacturing
- Media
- Policies
- Regulatory Learning
- Smart Cities & Regions
- SME & Start-ups
- Social Innovation & Inclusion
- Urban

Main Expertise

 User & Living Lab Research						
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TURKEY

Effective Member

BAŞAKŞEHİR LIVING LAB

Başakşehir Municipality

Country: Turkey

www.basaksehirlivinglab.com

Type of Living Lab:

Urban Living Lab

Başakşehir Living Lab is certificated as Turkey’s first Living Lab in May 2012. Başakşehir Living Lab is established for spreading innovation and entrepreneurship based on ICT and industrial design, supporting the new business opportunities, developing new easily accessible services for Başakşehir citizens, and promoting the awareness of citizens to new technological improvements. Başakşehir Living Lab serves at Başakşehir Municipality Innovation and Technology Center, located in Başakşehir District of Istanbul, where it is equipped with the latest technology and is the first public sector building that has LEED Gold Certification. In total, it has 3,000 sqm indoor space and many specialized areas in it, such as user experience centre, electronic lab, 3D modelling and printing area, incubation area, design factory, conference room, workshop hall and social area. In this building, entrepreneurs have great chances about user-centric application and product development, laboratory work, business development workshops and meeting with investors.

Areas of Work

- AI and Emerging technologies
- Circular Economy
- Culture & Creativity (creative sectors)
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Energy
- Environment/Climate Change
- Health & Well Being
- Industries & Manufacturing
- Media
- Mobility
- Policies
- Smart Cities & Regions
- SME & Start-ups
- Social Innovation & Inclusion
- Urban
- Water (Blue economy)
- Zero Pollution & Decarbonization

Main Expertise

 Living Lab Evaluation						
 User & Living Lab Research						

Adherent Member

Bodrum Living Lab
Bodrum Girişimcilik A.Ş.

Country: Turkey

www.bodrumlivinglab.com

Type of Living Lab:

Urban Living Lab
Rural Living Lab
Startup Accelerator

Bodrum Living Lab (BoLL) is an enabling co-creation hub where innovative products and services are developed in real life environments and with real users, coordinating all stakeholders of a start-up or a project (public, private sector, universities, and local citizens). BoLL aspires to play a key role in bringing all stakeholders of Bodrum to co-innovate and bring value creating projects into life. It focuses on Bodrum’s key economic activities: maritime, tourism, agriculture, and wellness. The Living Lab invites all innovators to join and create value for Bodrum.

Areas of Work

- Agriculture & (Agri-)Food
- Environment/Climate Change
- Smart Cities & Regions
- SME & Start-ups
- Water (Blue economy)
- Zero Pollution & Decarbonization

Main Expertise

 Scaling-up						
 User & Living Lab Research						

Adherent Member

Mezopotamya Living Lab

Şanlıurfa Metropolitan Municipality

Country: Turkey

www.mezopotamyall.com

Type of Living Lab:

Urban Living Lab
Rural Living Lab

Mezopotamya Living Lab's goal is to raise the living standards of the residents and to move beyond the standards offered by the Şanlıurfa metropolitan municipality. It does so by using technology accordingly and consciously in every aspect of life in coordination with the non-governmental organizations of the region, cooperatives of farmers and Professional chambers. The Living Lab provides value to different spheres of the economy. With ECOTECHNOLOGY AGRICULTURE and RENEWABLE ENERGY, it develops the land with technology and aims to benefit from natural energy. With SMART TOURISM and CULTURE, it seeks to see the actual value of technology in world tourism with all the possibilities at zero point in history. With INFORMATICS, ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE and INNOVATION, it works continuously with current trainings and mentor support to ensure that ideas and initiatives have a say in the world market. Their focal point are young people who produce technology and software for the world by developing technological products that are in every aspect of our lives, and by developing and raising their software skills to higher levels.

Areas of Work

- Agriculture & (Agri-)Food
- AI and Emerging technologies
- Circular Economy
- Culture & Creativity (creative sectors)
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Environment/Climate Change
- Industries & Manufacturing
- Media
- Policies
- Regulatory Learning
- Rural
- Smart Cities & Regions
- SME & Start-ups
- Social Innovation & Inclusion
- Urban
- Water (Blue economy)

Main Expertise

 Stakeholder Engagement						
 User & Living Lab Research						

UNITED
KINGDOM

Effective Member

Bristol Living Lab
Knowle West Media Centre

Country: United Kingdom

<https://kwmc.org.uk>

Type of Living Lab:

Urban Living Lab

The mission of the Living Lab is “Making fair and thriving neighbourhoods with art, tech & care”. Bristol Living Lab is run by Knowle West Media Centre (KWMC), a UK based non-profit arts organisation with 20 years’ experience of working with communities and individuals to understand how creativity and digital technologies can be utilised to meet local needs and address system change. It is a community based ‘enabler-driven’ Living Lab: KWMC acts as a ‘broker’ between citizens and organisations, ensuring that each participant in a particular project is able to contribute their knowledge and experience. KWMC adopts an ‘action research’ approach, where continual reflection and evaluation are built into the working process, and this enables KWMC to be flexible and responsive to the changing needs of partners and communities. It has a wide range of citywide, regional, and international networks that it actively works with and takes a ‘Commons’ Approach to sharing knowledge and learning.

Areas of Work

- Circular Economy
- Culture & Creativity (creative sectors)
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Environment/Climate Change
- Health & Well Being
- Regulatory Learning
- SME & Start-ups
- Soil

Main Expertise

 Living Lab Evaluation						
 User & Living Lab Research						

Effective Member

City Lab Coventry
Coventry University

Country: United Kingdom

Type of Living Lab:

Urban Living Lab

City Lab Coventry is an urban research-driven living lab drawing on the expertise and networks of staff from across Coventry University, providing an open environment for participatory research projects and initiatives. Particular areas of interest and expertise include circular economy, education and training, health and wellbeing, mobility, smart cities and urban areas, and social innovation and inclusion. We aim to work with and bring together a diverse range of local, national, and international partners and stakeholders, including SMEs, local communities, NGOs, charitable organizations, governmental departments, universities, and research organizations, to generate co-created, multi-disciplinary research-based knowledge and deliver outcomes with international significance.

Areas of Work

- Circular Economy
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Health & Well Being
- Mobility
- Smart Cities & Regions
- Social Innovation & Inclusion
- Urban
- Other areas of work

Main Expertise

 Real-life Experimentation						
 User & Living Lab Research						

Effective Member

Digital Health and Care Innovation Centre and Moray Rural Centre of Excellence and StrathLab

University of Strathclyde

Country: United Kingdom

www.dhi-scotland.com

Type of Living Lab:

Living testbed
Rural Living Lab
Research driven Living Lab

DHI is one of Scotland's 4 active Innovation Centres devoted to new digital technologies for health and care of citizens. Its mission is to enhance the populations longevity and health stimulating the economy, collaborating, co-designing and transforming innovative ideas into solutions by providing engagement, facilitation, project management, services, business and technical innovation using Living Lab Methodology. Funded by the UK Government, DHI leads the Rural Centre of Excellence for Digital Health and Care Innovation in the Moray Region (RCE) aimed at mobilising health and care services. The RCE identified 5 areas explored via Living Labs, supported by a Citizen Panel and underpinned by a virtual R&D infrastructure: supported self-management – working with industry and public sector partners to innovate a digitally integrated solution to support weight management and active; long term conditions co-management; care In place; smart housing/smart communities; mental wellbeing.

Areas of Work

- AI and Emerging technologies
- Health & Well Being
- Research
- Rural
- Soil

Main Expertise

Business Model Innovation	Co-creation Methods & Tools	Governance Models	Impact Assessments	Implementation after Testing	Innovation Strategies	Living Lab Evaluation
Panel Management	Policy Making	Real-life Experimentation	Scaling-up	Service Design	Stakeholder Engagement	User & Living Lab Research

Adherent Member

Lab4Living

Sheffield Hallam University

Country: United Kingdom

www.lab4living.org.uk

Type of Living Lab:

Research driven Living Lab

Lab4Living is a trans-disciplinary research group, based on a collaborative community of researchers in design, healthcare, and creative practices. These work together to address real world issues that impact on health and wellbeing, developing products, services and interventions that promote dignity and enhance quality of life.

Areas of Work

- Health & Well Being

Main Expertise

Co-creation Methods & Tools	Impact Assessments	Innovation Strategies	Living Lab Evaluation	Panel Management	Policy Making	Real-life Experimentation
Service Design	Stakeholder Engagement	User & Living Lab Research				

Adherent Member

Newcastle Living Lab

Northumbria University

Country: United Kingdom

Type of Living Lab:

Living Lab as a service
Research driven Living Lab

The Newcastle Living Lab (@NclLivingLab) is a method and set of tools that enable organisations to innovate their relationships with employees, partners, and customers. By analysing fundamental interactions, it can help to identify inventive approaches to wicked problems and better ways of getting things done. It represents a creative and innovative approach to complex problem solving for businesses and communities through collaboration and partnership building. One example highlighted how multi-agency collaboration facilitated by the Living Lab has helped transform the probation. By analysing fundamental interactions, it can help to identify inventive approaches to wicked problems and better ways of getting things done. It represents a creative and innovative approach to complex problem solving for businesses and communities through collaboration and partnership building.

Areas of Work

- Culture & Creativity (creative sectors)
- Education and/or Vocational Training
- Environment/Climate Change
- Health & Well Being
- Industries & Manufacturing
- Policies
- Regulatory Learning
- Rural
- Smart Cities & Regions
- SME & Start-ups
- Social Innovation & Inclusion
- Urban
- Zero Pollution & Decarbonization

Main Expertise

Business Model Innovation	Co-creation Methods & Tools	Governance Models	Impact Assessments	Implementation after Testing	Innovation Strategies	Living Lab Evaluation
Policy Making	Real-life Experimentation	Scaling-up	Service Design	Stakeholder Engagement		

Adherent Member

The Innovate Dementia Transnational Living Lab

Centre for Collaborative Innovation in Dementia at Liverpool John Moores University

Country: United Kingdom

www.ljmu.ac.uk/research/centres-and-institutes/centre-for-collaborative-innovation-in-dementia

Type of Living Lab:

Living testbed
Living Lab as a service
Research driven Living Lab

The Innovate Dementia Transnational Living Lab hosted by the Centre for Collaborative Innovation in Dementia at Liverpool John Moores University is a research-to-innovation asset. The Lab arose out of the successes of the Innovate Dementia project. The central aim of the project was to engage with people living with dementia to develop innovative ways of addressing their everyday challenges. The project team worked with people living with dementia, the business sector – SMEs and multinational companies, other academics, and commissioners and providers of services. Transnationally over 15 innovations were brought to the market. The work of the project was based on a robust participatory engagement process, in 2014 the Centre’s Living Lab was accredited by ENoLL. The Lab has widened its reach by working with co-creation groups across health and social care, this work is not always condition specific, it can be international; however, it is always grounded within the needs of the most vulnerable in society. The civic intention of the Centre is to facilitate people living with a health-related condition to develop sustainable solutions to their everyday challenges, while evaluating the real-world effectiveness of these solutions. Since 2012, the Centre has worked in partnership with both national and international partners on several research-to-innovation projects, securing nearly £20 millions of funding. During the delivery of these projects, the Centre has produced over eighty diverse research-to-innovation outputs.

Areas of Work

- Health & Well Being
- SME & Start-ups
- Social Innovation & Inclusion

Main Expertise

Business Model Innovation	Co-creation Methods & Tools	Governance Models	Impact Assessments	Implementation after Testing	Innovation Strategies	Living Lab Evaluation
Panel Management	Policy Making	Real-life Experimentation	Scaling-up	Service Design	Stakeholder Engagement	User & Living Lab Research

European Network of Living Labs
Living Lab Community

The international, non-profit, independent association of benchmarked Living Labs.

A yellow speech bubble containing the text "European Network of Living Labs".

**European
Network of
Living Labs**

A large, abstract graphic consisting of a thick white ribbon that loops and swirls across the purple background. A yellow circle is partially obscured by the ribbon's loops.

 www.enoll.org
 info@enoll.org
 [@openlivinglabs](https://twitter.com/openlivinglabs)